

Deliverable number (D2.1)

CET PUBLIC GOVERNANCE GUIDE

AUTHOR: EURAC RESERCH/GOBIERNO DE NAVARRA

DATE: 28/02/2025

DOC. VERSION: 1

LIFE CET Programme 2022 · **Grant Agreement N° 101120316.**

Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Technical References

PROJECT ACRONYM	PLAN4CET
PROJECT TITLE	IMPROVING CLEAN ENERGY TRANSITION PLANNING AT LOCAL AND REGIONAL LEVEL
GRANT NUMBER	101120316
PROJECT COORDINATOR	NAME: MAIDER ARREGUI OSES ENTITY: GOVERNMENT OF NAVARRA EMAIL: MAIDER.ARREGUI.OSES@NAVARRA.ES
PROJECT DURATION	SEPTEMBER 2023 – FEBRUARY 2026

DELIVERABLE NO.	2.1
DISSEMINATION LEVEL ¹	PU
WORK PACKAGE	WP2
TASK	T2.1 – T2.2
LEAD BENEFICIARY	EURAC RESEARCH
CONTRIBUTING BENEFICIARY(IES)	GOBIERNO DE NAVARRA
DUE DATE OF	28/02/2025
ACTUAL SUBMISSION	28/02/2025

¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

V	DATE	BENEFICIARY	AUTHOR/REVIEWER
1	15/11/2024	EURAC RESEARCH	GRAZIA GIACOVELLI, FEDERICO VOLTOLINI
1.1	15/01/2025	EURAC RESEARCH	GRAZIA GIACOVELLI, FEDERICO VOLTOLINI
2	17/01/2025	GOBIERNO DE NAVARRA	JON LOPEZ LUMBRERAS
3	20/02/2025	EURAC RESEARCH	GRAZIA GIACOVELLI, FEDERICO VOLTOLINI, ALICE BORSARI
4	25/02/2025	NASUVINSA	ENARA RABINA, YAEL LOREA
5	26/02/2025	GOBIERNO DE NAVARRA	JON LOPEZ LUMBRERAS
6	26/02/2025	EURAC RESEARCH	GRAZIA GIACOVELLI, FEDERICO VOLTOLINI, ALICE BORSARI

PLAN4CET

Cities and urban areas have been identified as the main opportunity in reaching climate neutrality, as they consume 78% of the world's energy and produce more than 60% of GHG. This need and vision are shared across EU cities and regions, but the climate neutrality transition process is complex, and many barriers have been identified. Even local and regional authorities have shown commitment to achieve climate neutrality, the lack of appropriate horizontal and vertical CET governance, integrated and holistic solutions and lack capacity (knowledge and resources) to develop and implement CET plans and strategies slows down the development of these process.

The general objective of the PLAN4CET project is to support European regions and cities to design, develop and implement Clean Energy Transition plans according to their needs and possibilities. To do so, the project has been conceived as an initiative where different project outputs (methodologies, tools and capability building and technical assistance) will be generated to support EU regions (specially to support medium and small unicipalities with a capacity lack) and cities in their CET planning, implementation and monitoring ctivities. The project will directly support 3 EU regions in improving the Climate and sustainable Energy Action Plans in pilots to be carried out in Navarra (ES), Skåne (SW) and Emilia Romagna (IT). These regions represent different type of EU regions and will serve as samples to many others in which the learnings and best practices can be transferred.

PLAN4CET will be executed by a consortium composed by a group of 11 entities located in 4 European Countries (Spain, Sweden, Italy, and Belgium), involving different type local and regional public authorities together with other entities. This project proposal was presented in the 2021 call, being favourably evaluated and entering the reserve list. It was not finally financed due to budget unavailability.

Summary

The transition to climate neutrality presents significant challenges, particularly for local and regional public administrations, which often struggle with fragmented governance structures, limited technical capacities, and insufficient financial resources.

This deliverable examines the role of public governance in enabling the transition to clean energy, with a focus on multi-level and horizontal interactions among public administrations. It explores how communication and social relationships promote cooperation and support effective policy implementation. By promoting integrated governance approaches, strategic participatory planning methodologies, and relational approach, the guide outlines some steps for identifying regional needs and offers practical tools and recommendations to enhance coordination, public administration engagement, and policy alignment across different levels of governance.

Building on the experience of pilot regions; Navarra (Spain), Skåne (Sweden), and Emilia-Romagna (Italy), this guide provides a solid foundation for adapting and scaling the proposed methodologies and strategies across different European contexts.

It serves as a practical resource for policymakers, planners, and decision-makers, particularly in medium and small sized municipalities, equipping them with the knowledge and strategies necessary to accelerate the CET and contribute to the EU's climate neutrality goals.

Finally, this report contributes to:

- Drive systemic governance transformation toward a multi-level and multi-actor framework, integrating both vertical (across different levels of government) and horizontal (across sectors) collaboration in both public and private domains.
- This shift involves moving from a traditional administrative approach in public administrations to proactively leading innovation across the public sector and beyond. It requires transitioning from fragmented, ad-hoc innovation efforts to a structured and strategic renewal of public-private partnerships, while also evolving from conventional human resource management to building innovation capacity at all levels of governance.

Spelling Guidelines

Standardised British Spelling (NOT Oxford Spelling!) should be used in all documents. Generic terms are spelled in lower case, specific terms and proper names are spelled with initial capitals. For metric tonnes use the term “tonnes” and NOT tons.

Disclaimer

Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Agency and the European Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Abbreviation

CET – Clean Energy Transition
SA - Stakeholder Analysis
SNA – Social Network Analysis

Table of contents

1. Introduction.....	10
2. Methodology.....	12
3. Setting the stage: Common definitions and identification of key public actors.....	14
3.1. Pilots.....	14
3.2. Assessing Governance knowledge within Pilot areas.....	15
3.3. Cross-sectoral approaches in CET.....	17
3.4. Multilevel governance in CET.....	20
3.5. Public Governance: key actors.....	23
3.6. Results.....	25
3.6.1. Italy: Emilia Romagna, Province of Parma, Municipality of Parma.....	25
3.6.2. Spain: Gobierno de Navarra, Municipality of Pamplona, Nasuvinsa.....	26
3.6.3. Sweden: Skåne Region and Energy Agency of Southeast Sweden (ESS).....	27
3.6.4. Key findings form the Organigram Analysis.....	27
4. Differentiation and categorization of stakeholders: needs and requirements.....	29
4.1. Respondents profile.....	29
4.2. CET policies.....	30
4.3. Needs, requirements and barriers.....	31
4.4. Governance system.....	31
5. Investigation of relationships in publics administration.....	32
5.1. Investigating formal and informal relationships in public administration: Social Network Analysis.....	33
5.2. Data collection and survey.....	34
5.3. Sample distribution.....	35
5.3.1. Spain.....	36
5.3.2. Sweden.....	37
5.4. Results.....	38

5.4.1. Spain	38
5.4.2. Sweden	44
6. Conclusion	50
7. Reference	52
8. Annex	54

List of figures

Figure 1 The analytical process behind the deliverable	11
Figure 2 Workshop's objective	16
Figure 3 Pictures of the workshop.....	17
Figure 4 Group 2 - workshop in Pamplona	19
Figure 5 Group 3 - workshop in Pamplona	20
Figure 6 Group 4 - workshop in Pamplona	22
Figure 7 Degree - Regional Government: Gobierno de Navarra.....	39
Figure 8 Degree - Provincial authorities.....	40
Figure 9 Degree - Local Government: Municipality of Pamplona	41
Figure 10 Degree - Local energy agency	41
Figure 11 Degree - Enviromental Associations.....	42
Figure 12 Degree - Relationship with colleagues: Gobierno de Navarra	43
Figure 13 Degree - Regional Government: Skane	45
Figure 14 Degree - Local Government: Skane	46
Figure 15 Degree - Local energy agency	47
Figure 16 Degree - Environmental Association.....	47
Figure 17 Degree - Relationship with colleagues: Skane	48

List of tables

Table 1 Sample distribution in Spain: Gobierno de Navarra.....	36
Table 2 Sample distribution in Sweden: Skane Region.....	37

1. Introduction

Clean Energy Transition (CET) is one of the most pressing challenges of the 21st century, requiring a fundamental shift in how energy is produced, distributed, and consumed. Effective governance structures are essential to ensuring that policies, regulations, and strategies align across different levels and sectors of government, facilitating a coordinated and just transition.

In a multi-level governance context, national, regional, and local governments must work together to implement energy policies that are not only ambitious but also feasible and widely accepted (Scholvin and Kalvelage 2025). The complexity of the transition demands cooperation, policy coherence, and trust between institutions, as misalignment between levels of government can lead to inefficiencies, regulatory gaps, or public resistance. Moreover, facilitating clear and efficient communication within the public administration is indeed essential to break down silos, improve interdepartmental cooperation and ensure that all actors are aligned towards common sustainability goals. Indeed, literature shows that when administrations understand the internal dynamics and informal networks that influence decision-making, they can better design initiatives that resonate with their workforce and accelerate the implementation of energy policies.

Finally, the success of clean energy and climate policies depends on the capacity of public authorities of stakeholder engagement (Abas et al. 2023), including private sector actors, and civil society, investigating needs and preferences that can inform governance institutions (Boyle et al. 2025). These aspects will be the subject of the Deliverable 2.2 of Plan4CET.

Within the PLAN4CET Project, given the urgency to understand the public governance mechanisms that enable a smooth and equitable CET, inside the present Deliverable, Eurac Research, Gobierno the Navarra and Nasuvinsa, prepared this report that contain tools and methodologies to asses the governance structure and interactions of public administrations at different levels and between different sectors.

The present Deliverable explores the role of public governance in facilitating the transition to clean energy, focusing on the multi-level and horizontal interactions among public administrations. It investigates how communication and social relations fosters

cooperation and policy implementation. Indeed, the ways in which public administrations communicate, both through formal and informal channels, play a crucial role in shaping governance effectiveness (Ayres 2022).

Moreover, identifying key actors within the different sectors and levels of public administrations and their communication patterns helps in tailoring messages that address specific concerns, motivate action, and build trust. Ultimately, a deeper comprehension of the social, human, and communicative dimensions within public administration can accelerate the transition to clean energy by promoting a culture of openness, accountability, and collective responsibility towards the planet. To this aim, the method of Stakeholder Analysis (SA) is was borrowed and applied to public administration.

Figure 1 The analytical process behind the deliverable

Gobierno de Navarra and Eurac Research worked jointly within the framework of Task 2.1 and Task 2.2 to firstly establish the methodology useful in the pilots (section 2) to achieve a common framework on cross-sectorial and multilevel governance between the partners and pilots of PLAN4CET (section 3). Then an analysis to identify the organizational structures and key actors of the public administrations (section 3.3), their needs and concerns (section 4) and the flow of information between sectors and levels of governance was conducted (section 5).

Finally this deliverable represents the achievement of the Milestone 3 of Plan4CET, regarding CET governance methodologies and the final version of D2.1

2. Methodology

A key factor in achieving the goals set by public administrations is the ability to coordinate efforts across different sectors and levels of governance (Tan, Mahula, and Cromptvoets 2022). Without effective collaboration among diverse actors—both within and beyond public institutions—policies risk being fragmented, inefficient, or disconnected from real societal needs. A cross-sectoral and multilevel governance approach ensures that decision-making processes integrate diverse perspectives, align policies at different administrative levels, and create synergies between governmental stakeholders (Bianchi, Nasi, and Rivenbark 2021). This not only enhances policy coherence and implementation effectiveness but also fosters innovation, trust, and shared responsibility in addressing complex challenges like climate change, energy transition, and economic development.

To effectively coordinate different sectors and levels of government within the public administration, it is essential to first establish common definitions and frameworks among the pilots, in particular regarding cross-sectorial and multi-level governance (OECD 2019). This shared understanding ensures consistency in objectives, methodologies, and expectations across different governance levels. Once a common foundation is set, the next steps involve identifying key actors, understanding their needs and requirements, and analyzing the relationships between them. By employing methodologies such as workshops, SA, surveys, and Social Network Analysis (SNA), it becomes possible to map the governance landscape, address potential barriers, and optimize decision-making processes.

The initial phase of a SA involves the identification of key stakeholders, in this case, key public actors. This step is crucial, as researchers and experts can gain valuable insights from actors who inherently possess essential knowledge by being directly involved in the context or process under examination (Kivits and Sawang 2021). A deeper understanding of their perspectives enhances decision-making by incorporating diverse viewpoints unique to each party. Following this, Reed et al. (2009) recommend distinguishing and categorizing stakeholders. This classification helps clarify their role in the process, their potential influence, what factors contribute to their satisfaction, and their individual or professional priorities.

The second step of the analysis involved administering a survey to identify and categorize the needs and opinions of stakeholders within the public administration at different governance levels. To systematically collect this data, a survey was developed within the Plan4CET framework, structured into key thematic areas:

1. CET Policies – Examining existing policies and their alignment with climate and energy transition goals.
2. Governance System Needs, Requirements, and Barriers – Identifying critical gaps, challenges, and opportunities for improving governance mechanisms.
3. Governance System – Assessing the overall structure, coordination, and effectiveness of governance processes.

The collected data enabled the identification of the most pressing issues, prioritizing them based on urgency and significance. This structured approach ensures that policy recommendations and governance improvements are evidence-based and aligned with stakeholder priorities.

The final step involves investigating the relationships between public actors (Vandenbussche, Edelenbos, and Eshuis 2020). Understanding these relationships is crucial for two main reasons. First, it provides insights into the current dynamics between various actors, which can be leveraged for collaborative efforts, such as advancing policy initiatives or implementing new strategies (Wilson, Heide, and Villeneuve 2025). Secondly, understanding these interactions fosters greater interdisciplinarity, which is essential in designing a governance plan that is adaptable and effective across multiple sectors and level of governance. Integrating diverse perspectives and expertise will ensure the development of governance policies and practices that are better suited to the specific context and needs of the stakeholders involved.

The SA has been used in different methodological fields such as economics, sociology, etc. this has led to problems in defining this method (Balest et al. 2016). According to Reed et al. (2009), these analysis: "(i) identifies the social and natural aspects influenced by a decision or action; (ii) determines the individuals, groups, and organizations affected by or capable of influencing these aspects, including non-human entities, inanimate elements,

and future generations; and (iii) prioritizes these stakeholders for participation in the decision-making process (Reed et al. 2009).

In the Plan4CET Project, a relational approach was used to identify the key actors involved. The project mapped the public actors to analyze how they interact with one another, how communication flows regarding the CET, and conducted a structural analysis to identify key players and understand the existing relationships.

3. Setting the stage: Common definitions and identification of key public actors

3.1. Pilots

PLAN4CET works on three pilots, which are located in Spain, Italy, and Sweden. These pilots represent collaborative efforts among regional governments, municipalities, and energy agencies, all aimed at advancing sustainable energy initiatives and achieving carbon neutrality through innovative practices and stakeholder engagement.

In the Navarra region, the project involves the Government of Navarra, specifically seven directorates, including the Industry and Energy Directorate, Rural Development, Environment, Spatial Planning, Telecommunications, and Territorial Planning. NASUVINSA, a public entity owned by the Government of Navarra, plays a crucial role by supporting municipalities in developing Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plans (SECAPs) and fostering local energy communities. The Pamplona City Council, the largest municipality and capital of Navarra, is also a key partner in the PLAN4CET project, ensuring regional collaboration in energy transition initiatives.

In Italy, the project is led by AESS, an Energy Agency that serves as a non-profit association for 153 public bodies, supporting the energy transition across various regions, including Emilia Romagna and Puglia. The Province of Parma is actively participating in the project to promote carbon neutrality by 2030 through transformative actions at all territorial levels. ATES Energy Agency, another partner, supports public bodies in Parma Province in their

energy transition efforts. The City of Parma, with approximately 200,000 inhabitants, is committed to achieving climate neutrality and is recognized among the 100 Climate Neutral Cities for its sustainable energy initiatives.

In Sweden, the Energy Agency of Southeast Sweden (ESS) operates across several areas, including Skåne, Blekinge, Kalmar, and Kronoberg County. As of January 1, 2023, it has merged with the regional energy agency of Skåne, focusing on the 33 municipalities within the region. The project benefits from the active participation of regional stakeholders, including the County Administrative Board of Skåne, Region Skåne, and the Skåne Association of Local Authorities, all of which have signed letters of support for various aspects of the initiative.

3.2. Assessing Governance knowledge within Pilot areas

During the Project Kick-off Meeting held in Pamplona in September 2023, Eurac Research, in collaboration with AESS (leaders of WP3), organized a knowledge base workshop involving the partners participating in the PLAN4CET Project. The workshop focused on the key themes of cross-sectorality and multilevel governance.

The main objective was to assess the existing knowledge base on these topics within the different partners and pilots. This understanding would serve as a basis for aligning participants' knowledge and ensuring a coherent approach to subsequent project activities. Starting from the reflection of two questions: (1) *What were your pilot's learning needs related to cross-sectoral approach?*, and (2) *What were your pilot's learning needs on multilevel governance with reference to each regions operations?* the group work began, stimulating the discussion on different fronts.

OBJECTIVE

- What were your pilot’s learning needs related to **cross-sectoral approach**?
- What were your pilot’s learning needs on **multilevel governance** with reference to each regions operations?

4 Groups
Figure 2 Workshop's objective

All participants, representing the PLAN4CET Consortium, were divided into four mixed groups, ensuring diversity across different pilot areas. Within each group, a spokesperson was designated to summarize and report the key insights from their discussions. After approximately 30 minutes of group work, each spokesperson presented a brief summary of their group’s findings to the entire Consortium.

In the following sub-paragraphs, the summary of the results collected during the KoM Workshop on multilevel governance and intersectorality for each working group will be shown.

3.3. Cross-sectoral approaches in CET

Group number 1 and group number 2 addressed the topic of the intersectoral approach by reasoning on three specific questions for each group. Below, for each question, the reflections that emerged within the two working groups are reported. In the following table you will find the answers that Group number 1 provided for each question during the presentation of their work:

Figure 3 Pictures of the workshop

How would you define cross-sectoral approaches?
<p>"For us, the cross-sectoral approach can be something horizontal that mixes different skills and sectors. It could be an office that manages different departments or sectors or units.</p> <p>This leads to an exchange of information between different sectors in the same entity or at the same level fostering the exchange of information that often does not take place between managers and employees."</p>
Which sectors are relevant and should we prioritize in your opinion?

"Here we should differentiate sectors by level (local, regional and provincial) as there are different issues and competencies (e.g. In Navarre, for example, the Region coincides with the Province). Important sectors are:

- Energy sector
- Environment department
- Urban planning department
- Social Services department
- Related to energy poverty
- Transportation sector
- Public buildings sector
- Procurement department
- ICT sector

Who in your opinion should lead cross-sectoral approaches?

"There are three options:

1. It could be led by an energy office integrating the different competencies we mentioned earlier,
2. If instead we are not only talking about energy transition as a closed sector, but we are also talking about climate and environment it could be led by another broader office

Include political and not just technical levels within this leadership."

In the following table you will find the answers that Group number 2 provided for each question during the presentation of their work:

Cross-sectoral approach

Figure 4 Group 2 - workshop in Pamplona

Which gaps do you identify in the current approaches?
<p>"We discussed different gaps we could identify, and we agreed that one of the main gaps is the commitment from the local decision makers.</p> <p>The commitment for energy related questions and this lack is in combination with lack of competencies and lack of resources."</p>
How would you ensure effective cross-sectoral collaboration?
<p>"There are structures in the city administration that make it difficult to try to collaborate in new ways. We have to break the old structure, and we have to look longer than just the four years of the election period.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It is therefore a matter of developing a more agile organization. On energy and environment, which will last longer than these four years of election periods, we need to ensure that the work is still going on, even if there is a political change, and talked about different ways to promote capacity building in terms of horizontal and vertical collaborations."
Which cross-sectoral best practices would you like to share?
<p>" We highlighted an example from Sweden. When we work with municipalities, to process SECAPs they have to sign an agreement. The commitment has to be constant, so an agreement</p>

guarantees their commitment.

The desire is to put together a group on energy made up of different departments of the municipal administration, the transport sector, the social sector and so on, in order to ensure a cross-sectoral approach."

3.4. Multilevel governance in CET

Group number 3 and group number 4 addressed the topic of Multilevel Governance by reasoning on three specific questions for each group. Below, for each question, the reflections that emerged within the two working groups are reported.

In the following table you will find the answers that Group number 3 provided for each question during the presentation of their work:

Multilevel governance

GROUP 3

- How would you define multilevel governance?
- Which levels are relevant and should we prioritize in your opinion?
- Who in your opinion should lead multilevel governance approaches?

Group 3

Figure 5 Group 3 - workshop in Pamplona

How would you define multilevel governance?
<p>"In our opinion there cannot be a single definition for all pilots because the territorial dimensions are different. For example, in Navarre, our municipalities are so small that they do not have technicians. That is why instead of focusing on what we mean by multilevel governance, we identified some problems (e.g., the levels need to better understand the needs from the bottom up).</p> <p>The conclusion is that there is a gap between the municipalities and the regional level, and we need to do something to bridge this gap and improve communication in a vertical way."</p>
Which levels are relevant and should we prioritize in your opinion?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - "Concerning the Italian pilot, the importance is the integration of both regional and national competencies while avoiding overlapping competencies is recognized. - For Spain, more attention should be paid to small municipalities, - Finally in Sweden both at the regional level, as 20 percent of the effort, and at the local level, as 80 percent of the effort should be directed to municipalities".
Who in your opinion should lead multilevel governance approaches?
<p>"We think leadership should be at the regional level, but should be a new actor independent of politics (example that does not change every four years, depending on elections) and should be an enthusiastic person.</p> <p>For example, in Sweden they have the Climate Corporation board. They coordinate some of the climate and energy issues, so it could be a good actor that sits between the regional government and the municipalities.</p> <p>Also in Spain and Italy there are local action groups, that could be also a new link. In conclusion the regional government should do something to promote and support them."</p>

In the following table you will find the answers that Group number 4 provided for each question during the presentation of their work:

Multilevel governance

GROUP 4

- Which gaps do you identify in the current ML governance?
- How would you ensure accountability, transparency and responsiveness in ML governance?
- Which ML governance best practices would you like to share?

Figure 6 Group 4 - workshop in Pamplona

Which gaps do you identify in the current multilevel governance?
<p>"In the current multilevel governance there may be several gaps:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The difference in political vision on each administration, which also depends on the political changes that occur every four years, 2. The second is the overlap between the same competencies, which leads to a lack of communication, 3. Difference in sensitivity. Different levels of sensitivity in different levels of administration or governance, <p>Lack of funds, but sometimes it turns out that it is not a problem of money, but how to use the money, how to distribute it".</p>
How would you ensure accountability, transparency and responsiveness in multilevel governance?
<p>" We tried to identify several strategies, one idea would be to hold a kick-off meeting involving all offices from all levels of this multilevel governance in order to get them involved.</p> <p>Another strategy would be to improve communication, both bottom-up and top down. Energy agencies might be a good idea to ensure accountability, accountability because they are intermediary bodies and they too. Independent, they are not tied to particular policies, parties or whatever."</p>
Which multilevel governance best practices would you like to share?

“ One example may be Spain, which initiated community energy in advance of the law at the national level, demonstrating good leadership. Another example from the Province of Parma was that it decided to include more actors than just the public sector such as NGOs to discuss and implement activities on clean energy”.

3.5. Public Governance: key actors

A SA, as presented in the previous chapter, of the Public Administration is essential for understanding the complex network of offices and departments that contribute to Public Governance. This analysis provides a structured approach to identifying key actors, clarifying their roles, and assessing their influence within the administrative framework. Given the often-siloed nature of public institutions, this process helps improve coordination by highlighting overlaps, dependencies, and opportunities for collaboration. A well-conducted analysis ensures that different entities at different levels work together effectively, minimizing inefficiencies and redundancies.

Furthermore, SA plays a crucial role in policy implementation. By mapping out the responsibilities of each department, decision-makers can allocate resources more efficiently and ensure that policies are executed in a coordinated and accountable manner. This process also enhances transparency, as it clarifies how decisions are made and who is responsible for specific administrative functions. As a result, it becomes easier to monitor performance, address inefficiencies, and ensure that public institutions are operating in the best interests of society.

In addition to improving governance structures, this analysis helps identify potential conflicts of competences among different departments. Public institutions often have overlapping mandates or competing priorities, which can lead to inefficiencies or policy contradictions. By recognizing these conflicts early, policymakers can take proactive measures to mediate disputes, streamline decision-making, and create a more coherent governance framework.

Another key advantage of conducting a SA in the public sector is its role in fostering citizen engagement and stakeholder participation. By clearly defining the key offices and

departments involved in decision-making, governments can create more accessible channels for public consultation and feedback. This not only enhances democratic legitimacy but also ensures that policies are better aligned with the needs and expectations of society.

Moreover, in the context of multilevel governance, where decision-making involves local, regional, national, and even supranational authorities, SA becomes particularly important. It provides clarity on the distribution of responsibilities across different levels of government, helping to reduce duplication of efforts and ensuring that policies are implemented effectively across jurisdictions. By defining the relationships between various actors, this analysis supports a more efficient, transparent, and accountable system of public administration.

The method we adopted for this analysis followed a structured two-step approach: First, we conducted desk research by reviewing websites, reports, official documents and articles of the Public Administrations involved. This allowed us to identify and map out the organizational structures, or organigrams, of each institution (see annex II). By analyzing publicly available information, we aimed to establish an initial understanding of the different offices, departments, and their hierarchical relationships within the administrative framework.

1. Once the preliminary organigrams were compiled, we proceeded to the validation phase. To ensure accuracy and completeness, we engaged directly with our designated contact points within each case study. The review aimed at providing necessary clarifications or updates. This validation process was crucial in refining our SA, as it helped to confirm the accuracy of the identified structures, resolve any ambiguities, and integrate additional insights that were not readily available through desk research alone. This validation phase was conducted through a snowball sampling approach.

This method allowed for the identification of additional stakeholders based on recommendations from those who had already been identified. The goal was to improve the quality of stakeholder selection, enabling a more precise and information-rich mapping. To facilitate this process, an Excel file was created and sent to all case study representatives, requesting them to identify any additional relevant individuals who had

not emerged during the initial phase. At the same time, they were asked to exclude those who, upon further consideration, were deemed less relevant to the CET context.

During this phase, it was essential to establish clear selection criteria for identifying stakeholders, including:

- Strategic relevance: an assessment of the impact that each stakeholder could have on CET's objectives.
- Potential influence: an analysis of the direct or indirect influence stakeholders could exert on key developments and decisions.
- Interests and expectations: an understanding of each stakeholder's specific interests and expectations regarding the project.
- Availability and accessibility: the ease with which stakeholders could be engaged in the process and their willingness to collaborate.

These criteria were fundamental in refining the stakeholder list, ensuring that only those truly significant for CET were selected. The combined use of desk research and snowball sampling resulted in a more accurate stakeholder mapping, fostering the inclusion of potentially overlooked voices and enhancing the overall effectiveness of the process.

3.6. Results

The desk research conducted on the organigrams of the public administrations involved in the three pilot regions—Italy, Spain, and Sweden—provided a detailed mapping of their governance structures, highlighting key offices, functions of each administrative system. This first analysis allowed us to identify institutional roles, hierarchies, and the level of coordination between departments in relation to the CET.

3.6.1. Italy: Emilia Romagna, Province of Parma, Municipality of Parma

The organigram analysis of the Region of Emilia-Romagna, the Province of Parma, and the Municipality of Parma revealed a complex and multilayered governance structure, where responsibilities for energy transition and sustainability policies are distributed across multiple departments and offices. The Region of Emilia-Romagna plays a strategic role,

defining policy guidelines and coordinating regional initiatives, while the Province of Parma oversees territorial planning, transportation, and infrastructure development. At the municipal level, the Municipality of Parma is responsible for the local implementation of sustainable policies, including urban regeneration, mobility, and digital transition.

A key finding from the organigram analysis is that while there are clear distinctions between regional, provincial, and municipal responsibilities, coordination between these levels remains a challenge. The presence of AESS (Agenzia per l'Energia e lo Sviluppo Sostenibile) as a technical support entity strengthens governance, but streamlining decision-making processes and avoiding overlapping responsibilities would enhance efficiency.

3.6.2. Spain: Gobierno de Navarra, Municipality of Pamplona, Nasuvinsa

In Spain, the organigram research of the Gobierno de Navarra, Municipality of Pamplona, and Nasuvinsa highlighted a high degree of decentralization, with several directorates involved in CET initiatives. The Gobierno de Navarra includes multiple directorates responsible for energy, environment, spatial planning, and digitalization, reflecting a cross-sectoral approach to governance. However, the absence of a unified coordinating entity means that responsibilities are dispersed across various departments, which could create difficulties in policy alignment and implementation.

The Municipality of Pamplona follows a localized approach, managing sustainable mobility, energy efficiency, and urban transformation projects. Meanwhile, Nasuvinsa, as a public agency supporting municipalities, plays a crucial role in the development of Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plans (SECAPs) and the promotion of local energy communities.

A key insight from the analysis is that while there is strong institutional engagement in CET, the governance framework lacks a structured mechanism for collaboration between departments and levels of government. This could lead to inefficiencies in policy execution, particularly in monitoring and evaluation.

3.6.3. Sweden: Skåne Region and Energy Agency of Southeast Sweden (ESS)

The organigram research in Sweden focused on the County Administrative Board of Skåne (Länsstyrelsen Skåne) and the Energy Agency of Southeast Sweden (ESS). The analysis revealed a clear and well-structured governance model, where responsibilities for energy and climate policies are well-defined and aligned with national legislation. The County Administrative Board of Skåne acts as a regional authority implementing national policies, coordinating with municipalities and overseeing compliance with energy and environmental regulations.

The Energy Agency of Southeast Sweden (ESS) operates as a technical advisory body, supporting municipalities and businesses with expertise in energy efficiency and renewable energy projects. Unlike the other pilot regions, Sweden benefits from a structured and hierarchical governance system, ensuring that regional energy policies are consistently implemented at the local level.

However, despite this well-defined governance framework, challenges remain in securing long-term funding for renewable energy projects and ensuring that climate adaptation strategies are effectively integrated into municipal planning.

3.6.4. Key findings form the Organigram Analysis

The analysis of organigrams across the three pilot regions revealed both strengths and challenges in their governance structures:

- Governance complexity and coordination: Italy and Spain exhibit a more fragmented governance structure, with multiple departments involved in CET, sometimes leading to overlapping responsibilities and coordination difficulties. Sweden, by contrast, has a more centralized and structured governance model, which facilitates policy implementation.
- Cross-Sectoral integration: Spain demonstrates a high degree of sectoral involvement in energy transition policies, but lacks a formalized mechanism

for collaboration between its directorates. Italy faces similar challenges, while Sweden benefits from clear interdepartmental coordination frameworks.

- **Role of Public Agencies:** The presence of AESS (Italy), Nasuvinsa (Spain), and ESS (Sweden) as supporting public entities is a common strength across all pilots. These agencies enhance technical capacity and facilitate policy implementation, but their influence varies depending on governance structures and institutional collaboration.
- **Monitoring and Evaluation:** A major challenge in Spain and Italy is the absence of robust monitoring mechanisms to track CET progress, while Sweden has more structured evaluation systems linked to national policy frameworks.

The desk research on organigrams provided crucial insights into how public administrations in the three pilot regions are structured and how responsibilities for CET are distributed. While each region has strong institutional engagement, improvements in coordination, policy integration, and monitoring mechanisms would significantly enhance governance efficiency in the CET. Moreover, the review of the organigrams led to the identification of several relevant public stakeholders. As explained in the methodology in the chapter 4.2, the list of stakeholders was validated with contact points in each pilot. Following the validation process, this collaborative effort has facilitated the compilation of a definitive list of public stakeholders to be involved in the upcoming activities.

4. Differentiation and categorization of stakeholders: needs and requirements

Multilevel governance is essential for a successful energy transition. The methodologies developed within the Plan4cet framework will serve to provide knowledge and tools to the regions and municipalities that are working on planning and CET strategies. In order to drive this systemic change towards a CET, it is vital to understand the needs and requirements of the end-users of this governance system.

Under Plan4CET project, a survey was conducted to collect the needs and requirements of end users regarding CET governance. This task will proceed with developing models and methodologies to develop and improve new procedures for the management and governance of energy systems. The objective is to provide regional and local governments with management tools to help them develop structures for better strategies for improved energy transition governance. Under this task, the needs and requirements that local and regional public administrations have to develop within their governance structures will be compiled. The target audience of the survey is political and technical personnel and citizens involved in CET. The sample to whom the survey was sent had been selected by each Pilot following those criterias and shared mainly by email.

The questionnaire was divided in 4 main blocks:

- Respondents profile (5 questions);
- CET policies (4 questions), Governance system's needs;
- Requirements and barriers (3 questions);
- Governance system in each region (6 questions).

The survey was available for a period of 4 weeks.

The full analysis of this survey can be found in the annexes A.3.

4.1. Respondents profile

The first five questions aim at collecting data and creating an overview of the respondents. 36 people answered the survey, but some surveys were not fully answered. Therefore, only the 26 complete responses were analysed. The 10 deleted surveys were uncompleted for at least half of the questions. This could have been due to a too extensive survey, and should be taken into account for future surveys in order to collect the maximum number of responses.

According to the region/partner to which the respondents belong, the distribution is more or less homogeneous, with the majority of the respondents (34,62%) from Navarre, followed by Emilia- Romagna (26,92%) and Skåne (19,23%). The remaining percentage represents other regions of Italy, Croatia, Ireland, and Brussels. These participants were contacted by the pilot's technicians.

Again, the gender distribution is relatively balanced, with 53,85% of males and 42,31% of females, while the remaining 3,85% preferred not to answer. When it comes to age range, the majority of the respondents are between 36 and 65 years old (84,6%) whereas the remaining 15,4% are between 18 and 35. This huge difference could be connected to the respondents' occupation and scale of occupation. While most of the respondents were professionals, for instance, project managers and project coordinators, namely type of role that are usually occupied by senior employees. In contrast, technician roles are often reserved for younger employees. This matches the answers collected in the survey. It is worth noting that almost 88% of the sample works at a local or regional level and only 12% is working at European level.

4.2. CET policies

Governments, businesses and citizens around the globe are facing the challenge of climate change and how to accelerate the global CET to reach net zero emissions by 2050 at the latest. Governments and policy makers have a key role in the achievement of these objectives, thus, it would be interesting to know the state of those policies on each of the pilot regions and see if they meet the needs and requirements of the CET.

The second block of questions was designed to collect the overview of each region in terms of CET policies and be able to compare the existing energy policies of each pilot. As a starting point of the analysis, it was interesting to know the existence of legal frameworks to promote CET in the regions/nations.

The survey showed that while all regions have some form of CET policy, these are not always well aligned or coordinated within a multi-level governance system.

4.3. Needs, requirements and barriers

The third part of the survey was aimed to collect the needs, requirements and barriers of governance systems according to respondents. The idea was to use this information to develop models and methodologies and improve new procedures for the management and governance of energy systems. The objective is to arm regional and local governments with management tools that will help them to develop structures for better strategies for improved governance of the energy transition.

Commitment of stakeholders and definition of common objectives appear to be the most important needs. Although important, policies involving stakeholders and the promotion of effective participation are not so important compared to the previous ones.

City administrations play a key role as the orchestrator of the uptake of smart and climate-neutral solutions in their jurisdiction. However, most of the respondents define its governance as a vertical one or a centralized one. Creating working groups or staff offices dedicated exclusively to strategic planning of crosscutting issues could be a good step forward.

Moving into the barriers the governance system might face failure to gain broad stakeholder support, not being able to implement actions and lack of commitment and involvement by the agents involved are the most important ones.

4.4. Governance system

Flexibility is a key feature of governance systems, as the need and requirements are not stationary and can change in the future. The GS should be prepared to cope with this changes. Although governments have a key role, citizens and stakeholders are an important part of CET governance systems. CET policies must ensure that consumers, citizens, stakeholders are actively involved, engaged, considered and at the heart of systems. This must be a smooth interaction, where the consumer does not have to think about their relationship with a complex system, but rather takes CET actions easily, in a frictionless manner. This type of interaction and level of engagement can be achieved

only through the design and delivery of CET policies that take the central role of the consumer into account.

The survey found that most participants agree that the governance system in their regions is too centralised and top-down, where reaching consensus among stakeholders is often difficult.

5. Investigation of relationships in public administration

In the Plan4CET project, understanding the needs and interactions of actors within the public administration is essential to facilitate effective communication and support the clean energy transition. To achieve this, a quantitative research approach was adopted, employing two structured questionnaires: one aimed at identifying the needs and challenges of public actors (see section 4), and another designed to analyze the network of formal and informal relationships among them using SNA.

By mapping public actors interactions and examining how information circulates across different institutions, this study provides valuable insights into the current governance landscape of the energy transition. The network mapping approach enables the identification of key actors and central nodes within the system, helping to pinpoint where communication flows smoothly and where barriers might hinder collaboration.

5.1. Investigating formal and informal relationships in public administration: Social Network Analysis

The Social Network Analysis (SNA) relies on three fundamental elements: nodes, ties, and boundaries (Borgatti et al. 2024). These elements form the basis for various research questions aimed at investigating different types of ties.

In the Plan4CET project, SNA was chosen as a method to analyze the relationships between different public administration actors and various levels of governance.

Our nodes consist of public administration officials working at both local and regional levels. The ties represent the relationships between these actors, particularly distinguishing whether they are formal or informal. Lastly, in the Plan4CET project, the boundaries are defined by two key entities: the Government of Navarra and Skåne, Sweden (due to the low number of responses to the questionnaire, it was not possible to conduct any analysis for the case study in Parma, Italy.). SNA enables the analysis of various aspects within any investigated context, allowing us to map a network where key actors, isolated actors, and bridging actors are clearly identified.

In many cases, actors who may appear marginal actually play a crucial role in connecting others who would otherwise remain isolated (Grandjean 2021).

By applying these principles, we can gain deeper insights into the network's structure and dynamics, identifying key actors and the roles they play within the system. To further refine this analysis, several descriptive measures were used to quantify the network's characteristics and better understand its overall connectivity and organization.

Density was used to determine the proportion of actual connections relative to the total possible connections, given the number of nodes (Bhattacharya et al. 2023).

Another crucial metric was normalized centrality, which assesses the average centrality of all nodes in the network. This value ranges from 0 to 1: a score close to 1 indicates a highly centralized network, where only a few participants dominate, while a value closer to 0

suggests a decentralized structure, facilitating a more even distribution of information flow (Borgatti et al. 2024).

Additionally, the Louvain modularity measure was used to evaluate the strength of community structures within the network. This metric compares the density of connections within detected subgroups (communities) to the density of connections between them (Ocelík, Lehotský, and Černoš 2021). Its value ranges from -0.5 to 1, where -0.5 signifies a non-modular network with no clear community divisions, and 1 indicates a structure where all ties are confined within well-defined communities (Dugué and Perez 2015).

To enhance clarity, Table A1 (see Annex) provides definitions of key graph theory concepts mentioned in this analysis.

5.2. Data collection and survey

Data were collected through the Computer-Assisted Web Interviewing (CAWI). The survey was written in English. Using the contacts identified through the activity explained in section 3.3, the survey was directly distributed by the three pilots. This approach aimed to leverage the trust and communication exchange already established between stakeholders and the pilots' key contacts to increase the response rate. Despite this effort, the number of responses for the Italian case study was very low, making any analysis impossible (only 2 respondents). Conversely, for the other two pilot cases, 31 questionnaires were collected in Navarra and 35 in Skåne. The survey was administered between late September 2024 and late January 2025.

The questionnaire began with an introduction that briefly outlined the research objectives, providing respondents with a clear understanding of the purpose of the study. It consisted of a total of 17 questions, divided into four thematic areas, reflecting the three dimensions of social capital: structural, cognitive, and relational. The final section of the questionnaire was dedicated to respondents' personal information. This methodological choice to place personal information at the end of the survey was made to facilitate completion, placing personal questions at the end so that respondents had already answered all other questions, thus reducing potential reluctance to provide their data (Dillman, Smyth, and Christian 2015).

The questions regarding relationships within multilevel governance in the survey were 6 and were structured as follows (for the full version of survey please see Appendix A2):

- For the regional government, please indicate the name and surname of up to three main persons you have been in contact with over the past 2 years regarding CET and the prevailing type of contact (formal/informal)?
- For the provincial authorities, please indicate the name and surname of up to three main persons you have been in contact with over the past 2 years regarding CET and the prevailing type of contact (formal/informal)?
- For the local governments or municipalities, please indicate the name and surname of up to three main persons you have been in contact with over the past 2 years regarding CET and the prevailing type of contact (formal/informal)?
- For the local energy agencies, please indicate the name and surname of up to three main persons you have been in contact with over the past 2 years regarding CET and the prevailing type of contact (formal/informal)?
- For the environmental associations, please indicate the name and surname of up to three main persons you have been in contact with over the past 2 years regarding CET and the prevailing type of contact (formal/informal)?
- Please indicate the name and surname of up to three main colleagues you have been in contact with over the past 2 years regarding CET and the prevailing type of contact (formal/informal)?

In this report, the analysis focuses exclusively on the relational aspect, considering only the questions related to this dimension.

We used RStudio for the descriptive analysis of our network through the .igraph package.

5.3. Sample distribution

In the following tables (Tab. 1 and Tab.2), the absolute values of the sample distribution in Spain and Sweden are reported. The variables considered are socio-demographic: level of

governance, gender, age, and experience. The question about the number of years spent in the current role was an open-ended question in the survey (see Appendix Annex 2), which was categorized during the sample analysis into four ranges: 0-1 year, 2-4 years, 5-9 years, and 10+ years. This classification was chosen as it could effectively represent both the level of experience and the length of time within that specific network, providing valuable insights into the respondents' relationships with different levels of governance. In fact, relationships are often built over time, and individuals who have been in their roles for a shorter period may have fewer connections compared to those who have held the same position for a longer time.

5.3.1. Spain

The following table (Tab.1) presents the absolute values of the sample distribution in Spain. In the column referring to "Experience Range," the total number of respondents does not match the other two variables (Gender, Age Range) because some participants chose not to answer.

Table 1 Sample distribution in Spain: Gobierno de Navarra

SPAIN	GENDER		AGE RANGE			EXPERIENCE RANGE			
	MALE	FEMALE	18-35	36-65	OVER 65	0-1 YEAR	2-4 YEARS	5-9 YEARS	10+ YEARS
LOCAL LEVEL	4	7	1	10	0	3	1	5	2
REGIONAL LEVEL	11	9	3	17	0	5	4	3	5

The gender distribution highlights a higher female presence at the local level, with seven women and four men, whereas at the regional level, the division is more balanced, with eleven men and nine women. Regarding the age range, most participants belong to the 36-65 age group, with ten individuals at the local level and seventeen at the regional level, while the 18-35 age group is less represented, with only one participant in the first case and three in the second. No individuals fall into the over-65 category, thus limiting the perspective of responses from this group. Analyzing work experience, the local level shows a higher concentration of participants with five to nine years of experience, followed by those with over ten years of experience, whereas at the regional level, the distribution is more heterogeneous, with a stronger presence in the 10+ years category. Overall, the

sample appears more experienced at the regional level due to a higher concentration of professionals with extensive experience. The most represented age group is between 36 and 65 years, suggesting that the sample mainly consists of individuals with an already established career. The limited representation of the 18-35 age group may influence response perspectives, partially excluding the viewpoint of young professionals, while the absence of participants over 65 further restricts certain demographic analyses.

5.3.2. Sweden

The following table (Tab.2) represents the distribution of our sample in Sweden.

Table 2 Sample distribution in Sweden: Skane Region

SWEDEN	GENDER		AGE RANGE			EXPERIENCE RANGE			
	MALE	FEMALE	18-35	36-65	OVER 65	0-1 YEAR	2-4 YEARS	5-9 YEARS	10+ YEARS
LOCAL LEVEL	7	6	4	9	0	2	5	5	1
REGIONAL LEVEL	10	12	3	18	1	1	4	6	6

The gender distribution at the local level shows a slight male prevalence, with seven men and six women. At the regional level, however, the distribution is more balanced, with ten men and twelve women.

Regarding age groups, at the local level, most participants belong to the 36-65 age group, with nine people, followed by the 18-35 age group with four people. No participants belong to the over 65 age group. At the regional level, the 36-65 age group is the most represented with eighteen people, followed by the over 65 age group with one person and the 18-35 age group with three people.

Analyzing work experience, at the local level, most participants have between two and four years and between five and nine years of experience, with five people in each range. They are followed by those with over ten years of experience, with one person, and those with zero to one year of experience, with two people. At the regional level, the distribution is more heterogeneous, with a greater concentration in the over ten years range, with six

people, followed by the five to nine years range with nine people, the two to four years range with four people, and the zero to one year range with one person.

In summary, at the local level, the gender distribution is almost balanced, while at the regional level, there is a slight female prevalence. The most represented age group is the 36-65 years, suggesting that the sample is mainly composed of people with an already established career. The low representation of the 18-35 age group could influence the perspectives of the responses, partially excluding the viewpoint of young professionals. The absence of participants over 65 further limits some possible demographic analyses. At the local level, there is a greater concentration of participants with between two and nine years of experience, while at the regional level, the sample appears more experienced, with a greater concentration of professionals with over ten years of experience.

5.4. Results

In the following paragraphs, the results of the relationship analysis for the two pilots are reported.

5.4.1. Spain

The following graphs represent multilevel governance within the Government of Navarra pilot. The nodes are displayed in three different colors: orange represents network actors at the local governance level, green represents those at the regional level, and white indicates actors who did not participate in our survey (meaning their position within the governance structure is unknown) but were mentioned by respondents. The size of the nodes in the following graphs is determined by the degree value of each actor. The larger the node, the higher the number of connections. The edges illustrate the types of connections between nodes: red indicates an informal relationship, blue a formal one, and purple represents both types of relationships. The arrows indicate the direction of the connections, as the underlying analysis is directional.

Regional Government Contacts for CET (Last 2 Years)

Figure 7 Degree - Regional Government: Gobierno de Navarra

Our network consists of 35 nodes and 53 edges, with a density of 0.0445. Nodes E15, E8, and E28 stand out for their high betweenness centrality values, highlighting their crucial role in facilitating communication. The graph has a diameter of 6, indicating a moderate maximum distance between nodes. The presence of 9 cliques with a minimum size of 3 reveals dense subnetworks within the overall structure. At the regional level, most relationships between different public administration actors are formal.

Provincial authorities Contacts for CET (Last 2 Years)

Figure 8 Degree - Provincial authorities

Graph 8 (Figur 8) represents the relationships within the provincial authorities. It comprising 26 nodes and 25 edges, this network has a density of 0.0385. Nodes E15, E25, and E8 stand out as the most influential. With a graph diameter of 3, it exhibits a more compact structure compared to the first network. The presence of a clique with a minimum size of 3 suggests strong connections among key nodes. In this case, for 5 public administration actors, it was not possible to indicate a contact person at the provincial level with whom they had any type of relationship regarding the CET in the last two years. However, it can be observed that most relationships occur between the province and the region, as most actors appearing at this level belong to the regional level of governance. Additionally, in the more consistent network composed of 20 nodes, all indicated relationships are formal.

Local governments or municipalities contacts for CET (Last 2 Years)

Figure 9 Degree - Local Government: Municipality of Pamplona

Graph 9 (Figur 9) represents the relationships between Gobierno de Navarra and local governments. The network depicted in Figure 9 consists of 49 nodes and 48 edges, with a density of 0.0204. Nodes E10, E25, and E5 emerge as the most influential. The graph has a diameter of 4, indicating good connectivity among nodes. The presence of 5 cliques with a minimum size of 3 suggests the formation of well-connected subgroups. This graph has 9 components because the central network, although quite dense, does not connect all the nodes, and there are other subgroups outside the central network.

Local energy agencies Contacts for CET (Last 2 Years)

Figure 10 Degree - Local energy agency

The figure 10 consisting of 18 nodes and 16 edges, this network has a density of 0.0523. Nodes E10 emerges as the most influential. With a graph diameter of 2, the structure is highly compact. The presence of two cliques with a minimum size of 3 suggests tightly connected subgroups. In this case as well, there are external relationships to what appears to be the main network of our graph. Additionally, these external relationships consist of only two nodes, indicating that this is one of those cases where 13 nodes reported having no relationships, while 3 nodes were able to identify only one contact person in the local agency.

Environmental associations Contacts for CET (Last 2 Years)

Figure 11 Degree - Enviromental Associations

The network 11 comprises 15 nodes and 11 edges, with a density of 0.0524. In this case, it isn't useful to identify the most influential node given the very low number of relationships. The graph has a diameter of 1, indicating an extremely compact structure. No cliques of at least three nodes were found, suggesting a less dense level of connectivity. In this case, there is no real network; the few existing relationships are only between a few nodes and are not interconnected. All the relationships indicated here are formal. Additionally, all the nodes indicated, except one, are outside our sample.

Your colleagues Contacts for CET (Last 2 Years)

Figure 12 Degree - Relationship with colleagues: Gobierno de Navarra

Finally, the figure 12 consists of 41 nodes and 43 edges, with a density of 0.0262. Nodes E1, E2, and E4 stand out as the most influential. With a graph diameter of 3, the network shows good connectivity. The presence of five cliques with a minimum size of 3 indicates the formation of well-connected subgroups. The graph 12 shows that at the regional level, there are many more relationships compared to the local level. Additionally, all the frequently mentioned individuals (E1, E2, E4) work at the regional level. Another interesting aspect is that regional-level ties tend to be informal, whereas at the local level, we find more formal ties.

Across all governance levels, some nodes struggled to identify three key contacts with whom they had interacted over the past two years on CET-related topics. As a result, isolated nodes appear in each network, even though they are not graphically represented. Specifically, the number of isolated nodes is as follows: 11 in Figure X, 22 in Figure X (provincial), 12 in Figure X (local), 21 in Figure X (local energy), 26 in Figure X (environmental), and 12 in Figure X (colleagues). The highest number of isolated nodes is found in interactions with environmental associations and provincial authorities.

A particularly noteworthy observation is that, at certain governance levels, two nodes indicated themselves as the only actors they had communicated with in the past two years about CET. This highlights a significant issue: individuals in these roles often lack clear communication channels and end up working in isolation. However, improved communication could facilitate the exchange of critical information.

Informal relationships play a significant role in information exchange within public administration governance. At the local level, 20 out of 48 relationships are informal, and among colleagues, 30 out of 43 fall into this category. In some cases, particularly at the local level and among colleagues, nodes reported both formal and informal relationships. This suggests that these relationships evolve over time, and many individuals exchange important information on a personal level. Our data show that those who report having informal relationships are often able to identify three key contacts within the public administration, which is less common for those who have indicated only formal relationships.

5.4.2. Sweden

The following graphs represent multilevel governance within the Skåne Region pilot. In this case, there are 5 graphs instead of 6 because the nodes did not indicate any relationships at the provincial level. In Sweden, there are historical provinces, known as 'landskap' in Swedish. These provinces date back to the medieval era and had their own administrative and legal functions. However, in 1634, the Swedish administration was reorganized into counties ('län'), which are the current administrative units of the country. Despite this, the historical provinces still hold significant cultural and historical importance. In the context of our analysis, the nodes did not indicate any relationship at the provincial level, which explains the absence of a sixth graph. This could reflect a lack of connections or interactions between the nodes within the historical provinces of Sweden. The nodes are displayed in three different colors: yellow represents network actors at the local governance level, red represents those at the regional level, and white indicates actors who did not participate in our survey (meaning their position within the governance structure is unknown) but were mentioned by respondents. The size of the nodes in the following graphs is determined by the degree value of each actor. The larger the node, the higher the number of connections. The edges illustrate the types of connections between nodes: red indicates an informal relationship, blue a formal one, and purple represents both types of relationships. The arrows indicate the direction of the connections, as the underlying analysis is directional.

Regional government contacts for CET (Last 2 Years)

Figure 13 Degree - Regional Government: Skane

The network 13 a low density of 0.029, indicating that the graph is sparse, with relatively few edges compared to the possible number of connections. This suggests that not all nodes are well connected, and the network is largely disconnected. The diameter of the graph is 4, which means the maximum shortest path between any two nodes is 4 steps, pointing to a moderately compact structure. Several cliques of size 3, such as {S13, S15, A10} and {S6, S10, S20}, indicate small, tightly-knit subgroups within the network. These cliques are likely to represent specialized relationships, though they are few in number. Centrality measures show that nodes like S10 and A4 have higher betweenness and degree centrality, suggesting they play more significant roles in connecting different parts of the network.

Overall, the network's structure suggests a few key hubs, but most nodes are less interconnected.

Figure 14 Degree - Local Government: Skane

Graph 14 (Figure 14) represents the relationships between Skåne Region and local governments or municipalities.

The graph 14 has a very low density (0.0153), indicating that only a small fraction of possible connections between nodes are actually present. This suggests the network is relatively sparse and not highly interconnected. The diameter of the graph is 3, meaning the maximum distance between any two nodes, through the shortest path, is 3 steps, indicating a relatively compact network. The cliques of size 3 identified (such as {S15, S21, S27} and {S10, S12, A34}) show small groups of nodes that are tightly interconnected, suggesting that, despite the overall low density of the network, there are highly connected subgroups. These groups might represent specialized connections or niches within the network.

Figure 15 Degree - Local energy agency

Graph 15 (Figur 15) represents the relationships between Skåne Region and local energy agencies. The network 15 consists of 50 nodes and 59 edges, with a graph density of 0.0241, which indicates a relatively sparse network. The diameter of the graph is 5, suggesting that, in the worst case, the maximum distance between two nodes is 5 steps. This is not excessively large, implying that the network is moderately connected, but not highly efficient in terms of overall reachability. The network contains 5 cliques of size 3, highlighting the presence of small, tightly connected subgroups within the larger network. However, given the relatively low density, these cliques are isolated from the rest of the network. Centrality measures, such as betweenness, show that certain nodes (e.g., S2 and S15) play crucial bridging roles, but overall, the network lacks high global cohesion.

Figure 16 Degree - Environmental Association

The graph 16 consists of 28 nodes and 19 edges, yielding a relatively sparse structure. Its edge density is quite low, at 0.025, indicating a sparse network with few connections relative to the possible maximum number of edges. The graph has a diameter of 1, meaning that the greatest distance between any two nodes is just one edge, which suggests a highly connected structure overall, despite its low edge density. When considering centrality measures, nodes S2, S8, S20, and others show higher betweenness and closeness centrality, indicating they play significant roles in connecting other nodes. However, the absence of cliques of size 3 or larger implies that the network lacks tightly-knit clusters of nodes. This could suggest that the graph may represent a more loosely connected network where central nodes are crucial for the flow of information or influence.

Figure 17 Degree - Relationship with colleagues: Skane

The network 17 consists of 62 nodes and 62 edges, with a low density of 0.0164, indicating that it is sparsely connected. The graph has a diameter of 5, meaning that the longest shortest path between any two nodes is five edges, which suggests some degree of fragmentation. Several cliques of size 3 are present, indicating the existence of small, tightly connected subgroups within the network. Notably, the presence of these cliques, such as those involving nodes like S2, S15, and S23, shows that despite the low density, some local areas are highly interconnected. The centrality metrics, such as betweenness and degree centrality, highlight the importance of certain nodes, such as S2 and S16, in maintaining the overall structure of the network.

In summary, the analysis of the network metrics reveals a sparse structure with key nodes playing significant roles in connecting various parts of the networks. Despite low overall

connectivity, tightly- knit subgroups and central nodes emerge as crucial elements. These insights are vital for understanding the internal dynamics of the networks and for informing strategies aimed at enhancing communication and efficiency.

6. Conclusion

Each public administration shall establish a multilevel and cross-sectorial climate and energy dialogue pursuant to national rules, in which public authorities are able actively engage and discuss the different scenarios envisaged for energy and climate policies, including for the long term, and review progress.

Collaboration between different governance levels and sectors is crucial to allow for delivery of the CET and the answers of the survey are aiming this statement.

To work in this, allowing for robust and consistent reporting mechanisms and integrate vertical and horizontal administrative layers is crucial. The delivery of innovative monitoring and verification schemes is also a working area to be taken into account.

It is worth mentioning that this survey and its analysis is a preliminary work carried out in a general way, with a small sample size that may not reflect the reality of each region in a completely faithful way. For further analysis, to conduct a specific survey for each region and a subsequent analysis by the technicians of each pilots could be interesting, because they are the ones who know the reality of their territory and community and the issues more relevant.

The results of this survey will serve as a basis for further elaboration of the multilevel and cross- sectorial governance necessary for the CET planning that will be detailed in this report.

In relational analysis, it would be interesting to understand why relationships on the topic of the CET are so sporadic, despite the fact that this issue is highly relevant and crucial for increasing sustainability at the municipal, regional, and national levels. Our network analysis provides a detailed view of the internal dynamics within governance structures, revealing that environmental agencies are not at all connected with the actors within public administration who deal with CET, both locally and regionally. This lack of connection creates inevitable disruptions in the flow of information between public administrations and local realities. These insights are essential for optimizing network efficiency and improving communication flows. Understanding which nodes are most influential and how they are connected allows us to develop more effective management strategies. Additionally, identifying cliques helps pinpoint key subgroups that contribute to network

resilience and robustness. Strengthening communication channels and fostering more interconnected relationships can significantly enhance overall governance effectiveness. It is important to explore this issue further, as the low number of connections between the various actors has led to a situation where two nodes, in both case studies, have identified themselves as the only points of contact on these topics. Regarding the type of relationship (formal/informal), the data is quite interesting. Although it is expected that relationships at the local level and among colleagues are much closer, it would be valuable to explore whether this impacts the information exchanged in formal settings. Specifically, this type of relationship could limit the active participation of certain nodes that do not have informal connections. Additionally, in the Spanish case study, some actors have been appointed at various levels of governance, highlighting some confusion about who holds which roles and responsibilities within the governance structure.

The pilots under the PLAN4CET project exemplify a proactive approach to sustainable energy transition, fostering collaboration among diverse public stakeholders across Spain, Italy, and Sweden. An example of best practices is the creation of working tables or task forces on CET that bring together public officers at various levels. By leveraging local knowledge and resources, these initiatives not only aim to achieve carbon neutrality but also serve as models for other regions seeking to implement effective energy strategies. The commitment of all partners involved underscores the importance of collective action in addressing climate change and promoting a more sustainable future for communities across Europe.

In conclusion, strengthening the connections between key actors at both local and regional levels and between different sectors is essential for improving the effectiveness of the CET. By fostering more interconnected relationships and ensuring better communication flows, governance structures can become more efficient and resilient. Addressing the imbalance between formal and informal relationships is crucial to ensure that all relevant stakeholders can actively participate in decision-making processes. Finally, clarifying roles within governance structures will help reduce confusion and improve coordination among different levels of authority.

7. Reference

Abas, Azlan, Kadir Arifin, Mohd Azhar Mohamed Ali, and Muhammad Khairil. 2023. 'A Systematic Literature Review on Public Participation in Decision-Making for Local Authority Planning: A Decade of Progress and Challenges'. *Environmental Development* 46 (June):100853. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envdev.2023.100853>.

Ayres, Sarah. 2022. 'A Decentred Assessment of the Impact of "Informal Governance" on Democratic Legitimacy'. *Public Policy and Administration* 37 (1): 22–45. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0952076720904991>.

Balest, J., M. Hrib, Z. Dobšinská, and A. Paletto. 2016. 'Analysis of the Effective Stakeholders' Involvement in the Development of National Forest Programmes in Europe'. *International Forestry Review* 18 (1): 13–28. <https://doi.org/10.1505/146554816818206122>.

Bhattacharya, Subhayan, Sankhamita Sinha, Paramita Dey, Anindita Saha, Chandrayee Chowdhury, and Sarbani Roy. 2023. 'Online Social-Network Sensing Models'. In *Computational Intelligence Applications for Text and Sentiment Data Analysis*, 113–40. Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-32-390535-0.00010-0>.

Bianchi, Carmine, Greta Nasi, and William C. Rivenbark. 2021. 'Implementing Collaborative Governance: Models, Experiences, and Challenges'. *Public Management Review* 23 (11): 1581–89. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14719037.2021.1878777>.

Borgatti, Stephen, Martin Everett, Jeffrey Johnson, and Filip Agneessens. 2024. *Analyzing Social Networks*. Third. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publishing.

Boyle, Evan, Alexandra Revez, Grainne Duffy, Ailbhe Farrell, Aoife Deane, Brian Ó Gallachóir, and Julia M. Wittmayer. 2025. 'Public Participation in the Development of Electricity Grid Infrastructure: Early Engagements and Community Forums'. *Energy Research & Social Science* 120 (February):103878. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2024.103878>.

Dugué, Nicolas, and Anthony Perez. 2015. 'Directed Louvain : Maximizing Modularity in Directed Networks'. Unpublished. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.4497.0328>.

Grandjean, Martin. 2021. 'Introduction to Social Network Analysis: Basics and Historical Specificities', June. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.5083036>.

Kivits, Robbert, and Sukanlaya Sawang. 2021. 'Stakeholder Analysis'. In *The Dynamism of Stakeholder Engagement*, by Robbert Kivits and Sukanlaya Sawang, 29–43. Contributions to Management Science. Cham: Springer International Publishing.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-70428-5_4.

Ocelík, Petr, Lukáš Lehotský, and Filip Černoč. 2021. 'Beyond Our Backyard: Social Networks, Differential Participation, and Local Opposition to Coal Mining in Europe'. *Energy Research & Social Science* 72 (February):101862.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101862>.

OECD. 2019. *Governance as an SDG Accelerator: Country Experiences and Tools*. OECD.
<https://doi.org/10.1787/0666b085-en>.

Reed, Mark S., Anil Graves, Norman Dandy, Helena Posthumus, Klaus Hubacek, Joe Morris, Christina Prell, Claire H. Quinn, and Lindsay C. Stringer. 2009. 'Who's in and Why? A Typology of Stakeholder Analysis Methods for Natural Resource Management'. *Journal of Environmental Management* 90 (5): 1933–49.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2009.01.001>.

Scholvin, Sören, and Linus Kalvelage. 2025. 'New Development Paths through Green Hydrogen?: An Ex-Ante Assessment of Structure and Agency in Chile and Namibia'. *Energy Research & Social Science* 120 (February):103904.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2024.103904>.

Tan, Evrim, Stanislav Mahula, and Joep Crompvoets. 2022. 'Blockchain Governance in the Public Sector: A Conceptual Framework for Public Management'. *Government Information Quarterly* 39 (1): 101625. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2021.101625>.

Vandenbussche, Lieselot, Jurian Edelenbos, and Jasper Eshuis. 2020. 'Plunging into the Process: Methodological Reflections on a Process-Oriented Study of Stakeholders' Relating Dynamics'. *Critical Policy Studies* 14 (1): 1–20.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/19460171.2018.1488596>.

Wilson, Christopher, Marlen Heide, and Jean-Patrick Villeneuve. 2025. 'Mapping Multi-Stakeholder Initiatives for Public Governance and Transparency: A Comparative Assessment of Trends and Motivations'. *Policy Studies* 46 (1): 24–45.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/01442872.2023.2282569>.

8. Annex

PLAN4CET

PARTNERS

Gobierno de Navarra
Nafarroako Gobernua

Ayuntamiento de Pamplona
Iruñeko Udala

Nasuvinsa
Navarra de Suelo y Vivienda, S.A.

eurac
research

FEDARENE

zabala
INNOVATION

ENERGIKONTOR
SYD

Comune di Parma

PROVINCIA
DI PARMA

AESS

ATES PARMA
AGENZIA TERRITORIALE ENERGIA SOSTENIBILITÀ

Annex 1

A1. Definitions of social network analysis

Network Structure	
Term	Definition
Network	A system of interconnected nodes linked by ties.
Directed Graph (Di-graph)	A type of graph where ties have a specific direction, represented as edges .
Directed Links	Edges that indicate a one-way relationship (e.g., advice flowing from one person to another). The connection may not always be reciprocated.
Degree	The number of edges the node has with other nodes in the network
Indegree	The number of ties directed toward a node in a network.
Outdegree	The number of ties directed away from a node.
Incident Edge	A tie that either originates from or leads to a node.
Density	The ratio of actual ties in a network compared to the total possible connections.
Path	A sequence of connected nodes and edges without revisiting any node. For example, if A is connected to B, and B is connected to C, the path is A → B → C .

Diameter	Longest shortest path between any two nodes in the network
Clique	
Measures of Centrality	
Term	Definition
Closeness Centrality	Measures how close a node is to all other nodes, based on the shortest paths. A higher value indicates a more central position in the network. It is often interpreted as the minimum time required for information to reach a given node.
Betweenness Centrality	Indicates how often a node acts as a bridge along the shortest paths between two other nodes. Nodes with high betweenness play a critical role in connecting different parts of the network.

Source: Based on Borgatti et al. (2022)

A2. Survey online – social capital and public administration

Personal data

First name

Last name

Relational dimension

1. What is your level of trust in the following institutions/actors involved in CET?

Actors	I have none	Low	Moderate	High	Not applicable/I don't know
Regional government					
Provincial authorities					
Local governments or municipalities					
Local energy agencies					
Environmental associations					
Colleagues ¹					

¹ **In all questions, the term 'colleagues' refers to public administration actors with whom you work closely (e.g. same office; same field) and with whom you have frequent contact.*

2. How willing are you to share information about new management insights or potential activities organized to enhance knowledge and promote CET with the following institutions/actors?

Actors	Not at all	Slightly	Moderate	Very	Not applicable/I don't know
Regional government					
Provincial authorities					
Local governments or municipalities					
Local energy agencies					
Environmental associations					
Colleagues ¹					

3. How would you define your relationship with the following CET institutions/actors?

Actors	Formal	Informa l	I don't know/Not applicable
Regional government			
Province Authority			
Local government (E.g. municipality)			
local energy agency			
Associations			
Colleagues			

Cognitive dimension

4. How much do your specific cultural norms and values influence your management of CET with the following institutions/actors?

Actors	Not at all	Slightly	Moderate	Very	Not applicable/I don't know
Regional government					
Provincial authorities					
Local governments or municipalities					
Local energy agencies					
Environmental associations					
Colleagues ¹					

5. How effectively do the following institutions/actors communicate with you about the CET governance?

Actors	Not at all	Slightly	Moderate	Very	Not applicable/I don't know
Regional government					
Provincial authorities					

Local governments or municipalities					
Local energy agencies					
Environmental associations					
Colleagues ¹					

Structural dimension

6. Currently, there is some bureaucratic resistance to CET; how much bureaucratic resistance exists between you and the following institutions/actors?

Actors	None	Not much	Some	Quite a lot	Not applicable/I don't know
Regional government					
Provincial authorities					
Local governments or municipalities					
Local energy agencies					
Environmental associations					
Colleagues ¹					

7. How often do you communicate with the following institutions/actors about CET?

Actors	Never	Monthly	Weekly	Daily	Not applicable/I don't know
Regional government					
Provincial authorities					
Local governments or municipalities					
Local energy agencies					

Environmental associations					
Colleagues ¹					

8. How capable are the following institutions/actors in solving problems in the management of CET?

Actors	Not at all	Slightly	Moderate	Very	Not applicable/I don't know
Regional government					
Provincial authorities					
Local governments or municipalities					
Local energy agencies					
Environmental associations					
Colleagues ¹					

9. Have you had any contact regarding CET with persons within the regional government over the past 2 years?

- Yes
- No

10. For the regional government, please indicate the name and surname of up to three main persons you have been in contact with over the past 2 years regarding CET and the prevailing type of contact (formal/informal)¹?

Name and Surname	
Type of contact	
Name and Surname	
Type of contact	
Name and Surname	

¹ In this research as formal relationships are considered the relations structured by official laws and regulations, involving defined roles and responsibilities, such as those of officials and institutions. Informal relationships, on the other hand, are based on personal interactions and unofficial networks in which decisions are taken through alliances and non-institutional influence.

Type of contact	
-----------------	--

11. Have you had any contact regarding CET with persons within provincial authorities over the past 2 years?

- Yes
- No

12. For the provincial authorities, please indicate the name and surname of up to three main persons you have been in contact with over the past 2 years regarding CET and the prevailing type of contact (formal/informal)?

Name and Surname	
Type of contact	
Name and Surname	
Type of contact	
Name and Surname	
Type of contact	

13. Have you had any contact regarding CET with persons within local governments or municipalities over the past 2 years?

- Yes
- No

14. For the local governments or municipalities, please indicate the name and surname of up to three main persons you have been in contact with over the past 2 years regarding CET and the prevailing type of contact (formal/informal)?

Name and Surname	
Type of contact	
Name and Surname	
Type of contact	
Name and Surname	
Type of contact	

15. Have you had any contact regarding CET with persons within local energy agencies over the past 2 years?

- Yes
- No

16. For the local energy agencies, please indicate the name and surname of up to three main persons you have been in contact with over the past 2 years regarding CET and the prevailing type of contact (formal/informal)?

Name and Surname	
Type of contact	
Name and Surname	

Type of contact	
Name and Surname	
Type of contact	

17. Have you had any contact regarding CET with persons within environmental associations over the past 2 years?

- Yes
- No

18. For the environmental associations, please indicate the name and surname of up to three main persons you have been in contact with over the past 2 years regarding CET and the prevailing type of contact (formal/informal)?

Name and Surname	
Type of contact	
Name and Surname	
Type of contact	
Name and Surname	
Type of contact	

19. Have you had any contact regarding CET with your colleagues over the past 2 years?

- Yes
- No

20. Please indicate the name and surname of up to three main colleagues you have been in contact with over the past 2 years regarding CET and the prevailing type of contact (formal/informal)?

Name and Surname	
Type of contact	
Name and Surname	
Type of contact	
Name and Surname	
Type of contact	

Sociodemographic information

21. Gender

- Female
- Male
- Diverse
- I prefer not to answer

22. Age

18-35

36-65
Over 65

23. Level of occupation
Regional level
Local level

24. How long have you been in this role?

25. Would you like to be informed about PlanCET project developments?
Yes
No

26. If yes, please leave your e-mail below

Task 2.1 – Annex A.3

Needs and requirements from end users

AUTHOR: JON LOPEZ

DATE: 04/26/2024

DOC. VERSION: 0.2

LIFE CET Programme 2022 · **Grant Agreement N° 101120316.**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

PROJECT ACRONYM	PLAN4CET
PROJECT TITLE	IMPROVING CLEAN ENERGY TRANSITION PLANNING AT LOCAL AND REGIONAL LEVEL
GRANT NUMBER	101120316
PROJECT COORDINATOR	NAME: OSCAR FERNANDEZ SEGURA ENTITY: GOVERNMENT OF NAVARRA EMAIL: OSCAR.FERNANDEZ.SEGURA@NAVARRA.ES
PROJECT DURATION	SEPTEMBER 2023 – FEBRUARY 2026

DELIVERABLE NO.	
DISSEMINATION LEVEL ¹	PU/PP/RE/CO (CHOOSE)
WORK PACKAGE	WP2
TASK	T2.1
LEAD BENEFICIARY	GOBIERNO DE NAVARRA
CONTRIBUTING BENEFICIARY(IES)	AYTO PAMPLONA, ESS, COMUNE DI PARMA, PROVINCIA DI PARMA, FEDARENE, EURAC
DUE DATE OF DELIVERABLE	
ACTUAL SUBMISSION DATE	

Index

1. Introduction	5
2. The survey	5
2.1 Respondents profile	5
2.2 CET Policies	6
2.3 Governance system's needs, requirements and barriers.....	9
2.4 Governance system in each region	14
3. Conclusion.....	19
4. Annex: Survey and Q&A.....	20

1. Introduction

Within WP2, a survey was conducted as part of task 2.1. to collect the needs and requirements of end users regarding CET governance. This task will proceed with developing models and methodologies to develop and improve new procedures for the management and governance of energy systems. The objective is to provide regional and local governments with management tools to help them develop structures for better strategies for improved energy transition governance. Under this task, the needs and requirements that local and regional public administrations have to develop within their governance structures will be compiled. This document is divided into three parts, matching the structure of the survey. The first describes the respondent's profile regarding origin, age range, and occupation. The second one is describing the background in CET policies that each respondent has and analyse by region. The final part is focused on the needs and requirements the governance system should have to promote CET policies effectively. [OBJ]

2. The survey

We will now analyse the results obtained in the survey of the different project partners. This survey was shared by the partners from the three pilots (Navarre, Skåne and Emilia Romagna) among different key respondents who are somehow involved in CET. The survey's first draft was designed by the Government of Navarra, and after a revision and some suggestions made by Eurac, the final version was handed to each pilot responsible for distributing it among key respondents, so that we can have a wider overview. 36 people answered the survey, but some surveys were not fully answered. Therefore, only the 26 complete responses will be analysed. The 10 deleted surveys were uncompleted for at least half of the questions. This could be due to a too extensive survey, and should be taken into account for future surveys in order to collect the maximum number of responses.

2.1 Respondents profile

The first questions of the survey (from three to seven) aim at collecting data and creating an overview of the respondents. According to the region/partner to which the respondents belong, the distribution is more or less homogeneous, with the majority of the respondents (34,62%) from Navarre, followed by Emilia-Romagna (26,92%) and Skåne (19,23%). The remaining percentage represents other regions of Italy, Croatia, Ireland, and Brussels. These participants were contacted by the pilot's technicians.

Again, the gender distribution is relatively balanced, with 53,85% of males and 42,31% of females, while the remaining 3,85% preferred not to answer. When it comes to age range, the majority of the respondents are between 36 and 65 years old (84,6%) whereas the remaining 15,4% are between 18 and 35. This huge difference could be connected to the respondents' occupation and scale of occupation. While most of the respondents were professionals, for instance, project managers and project coordinators, namely type of role that are usually occupied by senior employees, whereas technician roles are often reserved for younger employees. This matches the answers collected in the survey. It is worth noting that almost 88% of the people work at a local or regional level and only 12% is working at European level.

2.2 CET Policies

Governments, businesses and citizens around the globe are facing the challenge of climate change and how to accelerate the global clean energy transition to reach net zero emissions by 2050 at the latest. Governments and policy makers have a key role in the achievement of these objectives, thus, it would be interesting to know the state of those policies on each of the pilot regions and see if they meet the needs and requirements of the clean energy transition.

Questions 8 to 12 are intended to collect the overview of each region in terms of CET policies and be able to compare the existing energy policies of each pilot.

As a starting point for this analysis, it would be interesting to know the existence of legal frameworks to promote CET in the regions/nations.

Half of the respondents (50%) stated the existence of legal frameworks to promote CET at both local and regional levels, 27% stated their presence only at national level, and 7,5% only at regional level. Normally this policies and their application follow “from top to bottom” structure, meaning that first an European framework is published, then it is restructured to create a national framework and finally a more specific framework is created to meet each region’s particularities. Therefore, it is unlikely the existence of only regional level policies without a national level. These answers could be explained with a lack of knowledge among people who are not directly working with these CET policies, this is confirmed as respondents from the same region have answered differently. Only 15,38% of the respondents answered that there is no legal framework at all. Again, the reason for this result is lead by same reasons mentioned above.

If we analyse the answers by regions, Skåne shows uneven answers where 40% answered that there is not any CET framework, another 40% that only at national level and the remaining 20% answered that both national and regional level. This could be led by the lack of knowledge among the respondents.

Switching to Emilia-Romagna, among the 7 respondents only one stated the non existence of frameworks, whereas, 2 stated only at national level, and the majority (4) answered both national and regional level, showing that the majority of people is aware of CET policies.

Finally, regarding Navarre, 2 people said that only a regional level framework existed against 7 people answering that both, regional and national level.

Q8, Is there any legal framework to promote CET in your region/Nation?

When asking respondents about the existing frameworks and since when they are in force, only 3 people skipped the question, matching with the 15% that said that there wasn't any legal framework in their region. Among people that answered, respondents from the same region/nation matched with the frameworks. Here are the most cited by the respondents:

- [Ley Foral de Cambio Climático y Transición Energética Klina](#) - Hoja de Ruta de Cambio Climático PEN - [Plan Energético de Navarra](#)
- [Miljöbalken \(1998\)](#) (alla verksamhetsutövare hushålla med energi och i första hand använda förnybara energikällor) Lagen kommunal energiplanering (1977) - Säger dock bara att konsekvenserna av en kommuns energiplanering på miljön, hälsan och hushållningen med mark och vatten och andra resurser ska analyseras.
- [Piano per la Transizione Ecologica \(PTE\)](#) [Ecological Transition Plan (national level)]; Piano Nazionale Integrato per l'Energia e il Clima (PNIEC) [National Integrated Energy and Climate Plan]; Strategia Regionale per lo Sviluppo Sostenibile [Regional Strategy for Sustainable Development]; Legge Regionale 17 Febbraio 2023, n. 17 "FVGreen" [Regional Law 17 02/17/2023 "FVGreen" -> Decarbonization by 2045]; Piano Energetico Regionale (PER) [Regional Energy Plan].

Concerning the alignment of regional CET strategies with national, European and international strategies, almost 89% of the people answered that their strategies are aligned. This makes sense because, as we said earlier, these policies follow a “top-down” structure.

When asked if the public objectives of energy systems are clearly defined, we can see that, in most cases, they are clearly defined and aligned with the energy transition. However, when analysing per region, these results differ. In **Navarra's case**, all the respondents answered that they were both clearly defined and aligned. For the **Emilia-Romagna region**, 70% stated that they are both clearly defined and aligned and the remaining 30% answered that they are clearly defined but are not aligned with the energy transition. Finally, in the case of **Sweden**, 60% of the respondents stated that these public policies are not clearly defined. This might be an issue to tackle to understand why these objectives are not clearly defined in the region. Without a clear roadmap that sets concrete objectives, it is difficult to make progress in CET.

Are the public policy objectives of energy systems clearly defined? Are they aligned with the energy transition?

Respondidas: 26 Omitidas: 0

Q11, Are the public policy objectives of energy systems clearly defined? Are they aligned with the energy transition?

2.3 Governance system’s needs, requirements and barriers

This third part of the survey was aimed to collect the needs, requirements and barriers of governance systems according to respondents. The idea is to use this information in future tasks of the WP for development models and methodologies to develop and improve new procedures for the management and governance of energy systems. The objective is to arm regional and local governments with management tools that will help them to develop structures for better strategies for improved governance of the energy transition.

Commitment of stakeholders and definition of common objectives appear to be the most important needs. Although important, policies involving stakeholders and the promotion of effective participation are not so important compared to the previous ones.

Here are some of the respondents’ comments in the open answer box for GS needs:

- *Coherence of measures and policies with the strategies and objectives*
- *Awareness of the citizenship*
- *Participation of the citizenship*

On a scale of 1 to 4, where 1 is the lowest value and 4 the highest, how important are the following possible needs for the governance system (GS) to achieve its objectives?

Respondidas: 26 Omitidas: 0

Q12, Possible needs of GS

Here we can see the answers divided by regions. Navarra's and Emilia Romagna's are more similar, whereas Skåne's results differ slightly. For Navarra and Emilia Romagna definition of common objectives are really important, whereas for Skåne, the definition of objectives is that important. This is in line with the answers of Skåne for the question Q11, where 60% of the respondents stated that their policies were not clearly defined. If the objectives are not clearly defined by the government, the rest of involved agents will hardly see this need as an important one.

On a scale of 1 to 4, where 1 is the lowest value and 4 the highest, how important are the following possible needs for the governance system (GS) to achieve its objectives?

Navarra

On a scale of 1 to 4, where 1 is the lowest value and 4 the highest, how important are the following possible needs for the governance system (GS) to achieve its objectives?

Emilia Romagna

On a scale of 1 to 4, where 1 is the lowest value and 4 the highest, how important are the following possible needs for the governance system (GS) to achieve its objectives?

Skåne

As for the requirements for the governance system, all of them seem to be quite important, being the Sustainability the most significant.

- **Strategy:** The definition of objectives and the implementation of activities, programmes or the operating system of the governance system. The short and medium-term plans that enable it to adapt its mission to the context in which it operates and the organisational structure it adopts.
- **Control:** Supervision of activities and professional staff and actions implemented at all times within the framework of applicable laws and regulations.
- **Sustainability:** Governance must ensure the proper use of funds and have the acceptance (and eventual support) of society for the development of its activities

The Use of quality tools and KPI should also be important requirements in the opinion of the respondents.

On a scale of 1 to 4, where 1 is the lowest value and 4 the highest, how important are the following requirements for the governance system to achieve its objectives?

Respondidas: 26 Omitidas: 0

Q13, requirements of GS

As for the requirements, once again the answers from participants from Italy and Spain are more similar compared to the ones from Sweden. It should be noted that due to the size of the sample being small, one single answers makes a significant change in the chart and maybe with a bigger sample the answers by region could be more similar.

Moving into the barriers the governance system might face *failure to gain broad stakeholder support, not being able to implement actions and lack of commitment and involvement by the agents involved* are the most important ones.

Barriers:

- Failure to gain broad stakeholder support and to prevent falling into an endless consultation process. Not being able to implement actions.
- Lack of commitment and involvement by the agents involved.
- Lack of resources (financial, staff, etc.)
- Lack of transparency
- 'Numbness or introspection', in which the GS is more concerned about himself than about advancing the organisation and its mission or adapting to changes in the environment.

Respondents' comments:

- *Lack of coordination between departments and different public administrations (local, regional,...)*

On a scale of 1 to 4, where 1 is the lowest value and 4 the highest, rate the impact of the following barriers on the governance system

Respondidas: 26 Omitidas: 0

Q14, Barriers on the GS

City administrations play a key role as the orchestrator of the uptake of smart and climate-neutral solutions in their jurisdiction. However, most of the respondents define its governance as a vertical one or a centralized one. Creating working groups or staff offices dedicated exclusively to strategic planning of crosscutting issues could be a good step forward.

2.4 Governance system in each region

Flexibility is a key feature of governance systems, as the need and requirements are not stationary and can change in the future. The GS should be prepared to cope with this changes. Although governments have a key role, citizens and stakeholders are an important part of CET governance systems. CET policies must ensure that consumers, citizens, stakeholders... are actively involved, engaged, considered and at the heart of systems. This must be a smooth interaction, where the consumer does not have to think about their relationship with a complex system, but rather takes CET actions easily, in a frictionless manner. This type of interaction and level of engagement can be achieved only through the design and delivery of CET policies that take the central role of the consumer into account.

Here we can see how respondents of each region define its governance system:

- Lack of consensus and organisation to implement certain actions, such as one-stop-shops integrating various services at regional level (energy rehabilitation, urban regeneration, inclusion of RES, energy poverty, renaturalisation, etc.).
- I believe that the local government has a clear objective of promoting local energy generation, rehabilitation of the housing stock, and passive construction standards, but with the mobility sector it is not acting in the same way. The percentage of energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions are too high in the mobility sector; there is much room for improvement in railway infrastructure, both for commuter and freight transport. I believe that changing from combustion vehicles to EV or hydrogen vehicles is not the solution. This strategy puts a disproportionate responsibility on citizens for the change in the model and what we really need is a change in the mobility model itself.
- Top-down and centralized. Most of the decisions are being made at the national level and passed down through the levels of governance without proper alignment
- Weak, there is room for to listen to and involve more the stakeholders and citizens and to monitor the implementation of the strategies and plans, respecting milestones and their time scheduling
- A common path: the new Covenant establishes shared commitments and responsibilities to improve the quality of life for people and the planet and overcome the conflict between development and the environment.

And here are some of the answers from the participants in how should it look like in the future:

- Real cooperation horizontal (between Navarra's Government Departments) and vertical (including Local Action Groups, Public Enterprises and Local Entities).
- Broader interaction between governmental agencies working towards the same goal, more implemented actions rather than investigations/reports
- Much more transversal than now
- I hope it will have a more bottom up approach with a strong coordination which is able to collect and properly harmonize all inputs received
- stronger governance with more mandatory requirements on the municipalities
- As I have said before, a change of mobility model should be developed, shared and multimodal. On the other hand, citizen-driven energy communities should be promoted from the bottom up, by citizens, without being dictated by energy companies.

Next charts show the involvement level of each stakeholder in order to achieve the following objectives

Establishing rules and principles to help manage and control organizations and instit...

Building an environment of trust, transparency and accountability.

Protecting the rights of shareholders and stakeholders in organizations.

Distribution of roles and responsibilities through tight organizational structures.

Coordinate alignment with national, international and European level strategies and e...

For most of the objectives, the involvement of public administrations turns out to be the most important stakeholder whereas in the opinion of the respondents; citizens have little to do in order to achieve the objectives. But researchers and experts agree that a good GS should have the involvement of all the agents mentioned above, so this must be taken into account.

Here are some key engagement strategies:

- The upscaling of clean transition capacity-building measures for the evolving energy system, to match (in magnitude of service provision and in delivery timelines) the goals of energy efficiency policies.
- The provision of clear, consumer-friendly energy-related information (energy use, rating etc.) for energy-related actions at or before the decision making stage.
- The inclusion of behavioural insights in the design of CET policies. Dedicated behavioural science teams should support policy makers in policy design and implementation.
- The sharing of best practices and approaches in a systematic manner.

According to the development stages of a governance system, most of the respondents appear to be on the second stage.

- **First stage:** GS members are relatively homogeneous in terms of personal thinking and commitment to the organisation. It is usually a fairly small council and tends to have a more informal structure.
- **Second stage:** It emerges when the organisation has achieved greater maturity and the GS's attention shifts. It focuses more on classic governance questions such as planning, oversight and accountability. Committees are formed and the number of directors increases. The consequence is a more defined structure.
- **Third stage:** GS members are strategically recruited, there are committees to develop the work, an executive committee to prepare complex decisions, and in some cases an advisory committee with external experts.

Q18, development stage of governance system

Finally the recurrent review and evaluation mechanisms that can help governance systems develop structures that improve governance strategies are:

- Fostering a culture of monitoring, evaluation and learning among public officials by increasing their capacity to regularly conduct exercises for these purposes in collaboration with relevant stakeholders (88%)
- Periodic review of regional and local KPIs to monitor targets and identify any early deviations. In the event of deviations, identification of their causes. Finally, application of corrective measures.(81%)
- Instruments for measuring efficiency: relationship between the resources used in the implementation of actions and the products and effects of the action.(54%)

Q20, Review and evaluation mechanisms

3. Conclusion

Each partner shall establish a multilevel climate and energy dialogue pursuant to national rules, in which local authorities, civil society organisations, business community, investors, other relevant stakeholders, and the public are able actively engage and discuss the different scenarios envisaged for energy and climate policies, including for the long term, and review progress.

Collaboration between governance levels and stakeholders is crucial to allow for delivery of the clean energy transition and the answers of the survey are aiming this statement.

To work in this, allowing for robust and consistent reporting mechanisms and integrate vertical and horizontal administrative layers is crucial. The delivery of innovative monitoring and verification schemes is also a working area to be taken into account.

It is worth mentioning that this survey and its analysis is a preliminary work carried out in a general way, with a small sample size that may not reflect the reality of each region in a completely faithful way. For further analysis, to conduct a specific survey for each region and a subsequent analysis by the technicians of each region could be interesting, because they are the ones who know the reality of their region and the causes that create it.

PLAN4CET

4. Annex: Survey and Q&A

PARTNERS

Gobierno de Navarra
Nafarroako Gobernua

Ayuntamiento de Pamplona
Iruñeko Udaia

Nasuvinsa
Navarra de Suelo y Vivienda, S.A.

eurac
research

zabala
INNOVATION

ENERGIKONTOR
SYD

Comune di Parma

PROVINCIA
DI PARMA

AGENZIA TERRITORIALE
ENERGIA SOSTENIBILITÀ
AESS

ATES PARMA
AGENZIA TERRITORIALE ENERGIA SOSTENIBILITÀ

Improving Clean Energy Transition planning at local and regional level

The general objective of PLAN₄CET is to support European regions and cities to design, develop, and implement CET (Clean Energy Transition) plans according to their needs and possibilities. To do so, the different project outputs (methodologies, tools, capability building, and technical assistance) will be generated to support EU (European Union) regions and cities in their CET planning, implementation, and monitoring activities.

PLAN₄CET will directly support 3 EU regions in improving their Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plans: Navarra (ES), Skåne (SW) and Emilia Romagna (IT). These regions represent different type of EU regions and will serve as samples to many others in which the learnings and best practices can be transferred.

The aim of this survey is to collect data to elaborate a guide that will contain the main requirements, barriers, and needs from different level of public administrations and a complete guide to prepare plans and develop or adapt strategies for the CET planification in the territory.

**The survey should take between 15-20 minutes*

**Collected data will remain anonymous*

OK

* 1. I consent to the collection of my response data by Plan₄CET for the purposes described in this policy and understand that I can withdraw my consent at any time.

Yes

No

* 2. Email address

NEXT

3. Region/partner to which the respondent belongs

- Navarre (Spain)
- Skåne (Sweden)
- Emilia Romagna (Italy)
- Other (Specify)

4. Gender

- Male
- Female
- Non-Binary
- I prefer not to answer

5. Age range

- Between 18 and 35
- Between 36 and 65
- over 65

6. Occupation

7. Specify the scale of occupation (regional, local)

Prev

Next

* 8. Is there any legal framework to promote CET in your region/Nation?

- No
- Yes, but only at regional level
- Yes, but only at national level
- Yes , both national and regional level

9. In case of existing framework(s) , could you name it (them)?Since when is in force?

10. Regarding your regional CET strategy, is it aligned with national, European and international strategies?

- No
- Yes

11. Are the public policy objectives of energy systems clearly defined? Are they aligned with the energy transition?

- They are not clearly defined
- They are clearly defined, but are not aligned with the energy transition
- They are both clearly defined and aligned

* 12. On a scale of 1 to 4, where 1 is the lowest value and 4 the highest, how important are the following possible needs for the governance system (GS) to achieve its objectives?

	1	2	3	4
Commitment of the stakeholders	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Definition of common objectives	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policies involving the stakeholders	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Promote effective participation and consensus building	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Other (Specify)

* 13. On a scale of 1 to 4, where 1 is the lowest value and 4 the highest, how important are the following requirements for the governance system to achieve its objectives?

1 2 3 4

Strategy: The definition of objectives and the implementation of activities, programmes or the operating system of the governance system. The short and medium-term plans that enable it to adapt its mission to the context in which it operates and the organisational structure it adopts.

Control: Supervision of activities and professional staff and actions implemented at all times within the framework of applicable laws and regulations.

Sustainability: Governance must ensure the proper use of funds and have the acceptance (and eventual support) of society for the development of its activities

Other (Specify)

* 14. On a scale of 1 to 4, where 1 is the lowest value and 4 the highest, rate the impact of the following barriers on the governance system

1 2 3 4

Failure to gain broad stakeholder support and to prevent falling into an endless consultation process. Not being able to implement actions.

Lack of commitment and involvement by the agents involved.

Lack of resources (financial, staff, etc.)

Lack of transparency

'Numbness or introspection', in which the GS is more concerned about himself than about advancing the organisation and its mission or adapting to changes in the environment.

Other (Specify)

15. How would you define the governance of your region?

16. What should it look like in the future/what do you imagine it will look like?

* 17. What should be the level of involvement of each stakeholder to achieve the following objectives? (select from drop-down menu).

	Establishing rules and principles to help manage and control organizations and institutions	Building an environment of trust, transparency and accountability.	Protecting the rights of shareholders and stakeholders in organizations.	Distribution of roles and responsibilities through tight organizational structures.	Coordinate alignment with national, international and European level strategies and encourage participation in EU or international networks and initiatives	Encourage the participation of citizens and social and economic actors in the development and implementation of planning instruments regarding CET
Citizens	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Companies	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Public administrations	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Professional associations	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Social environmental associations	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

Other (Specify)

18. According to the following development stages of a governance system, in which stage is your region currently?

- **First stage:** GS members are relatively homogeneous in terms of personal thinking and commitment to the organisation. It is usually a fairly small council and tends to have a more informal structure.

- **Second stage:** *It emerges when the organisation has achieved greater maturity and the GS's attention shifts. It focuses more on classic governance questions such as planning, oversight and accountability. Committees are formed and the number of directors increases. The consequence is a more defined structure.*

- **Third stage:** *GS members are strategically recruited, there are committees to develop the work, an executive committee to prepare complex decisions, and in some cases an advisory committee with external experts.*

- First stage
- Second stage
- Third stage

19. What management tools can help governance systems develop structures that improve governance strategies?

For instance:

- Collection of regional energy data from multiple sources to prepare the Navarre Energy Balance (annual) to monitor regional KPIs (PEN2030).

- Use of statistical tools and technology platforms to monitor energy management at local and regional level (EIS in Navarra).

- The creation of a monitoring tool for SECAPs (agreements reached, planning and actions executed and monitoring of results).

* 20. Define which review and evaluation mechanisms the governance system should have in order to detect early on possible deviations from the achievement of the objectives.
(Multiple choice)

Fostering a culture of monitoring, evaluation and learning among public officials by increasing their capacity to regularly conduct exercises for these purposes in collaboration with relevant stakeholders.

Identifying institutional actors to be in charge of collecting and disseminating up-to-date and reliable information and data in an open format.

Periodic review of regional and local KPIs to monitor targets and identify any early deviations. In the event of deviations, identification of their causes. Finally, application of corrective measures.

Critical points balance sheets

Instruments for measuring efficiency: relationship between the resources used in the implementation of actions and the products and effects of the action.

Other (please specify)

P3 Region/partner to which the respondent belongs

Respondidas: 26 Omitidas: 0

OPCIONES DE RESPUESTA	RESPUESTAS	
Navarre (Spain)	34.62%	9
Skåne (Sweden)	19.23%	5
Emilia Romagna (Italy)	26.92%	7
Other (Specify)	19.23%	5
TOTAL		26

#	OTHER (SPECIFY)	DATE
1	Brussels	3/6/2024 1:25 PM
2	Friuli Venezia Giulia	3/5/2024 9:57 AM
3	Italy	3/5/2024 9:42 AM
4	Croatia	3/4/2024 11:26 AM
5	Ireland	3/1/2024 6:23 PM

P4 Gender

Respondidas: 26 Omitidas: 0

OPCIONES DE RESPUESTA	RESPUESTAS	
Male	53.85%	14
Female	42.31%	11
Non-Binary	0.00%	0
I prefer not to answer	3.85%	1
Other (Specify)	0.00%	0
TOTAL		26

#	OTHER (SPECIFY)	DATE
There are no responses.		

P5 Age range

Respondidas: 26 Omitidas: 0

OPCIONES DE RESPUESTA	RESPUESTAS	
Under 18	0.00%	0
Between 18 and 35	15.38%	4
Between 36 and 65	84.62%	22
over65	0.00%	0
TOTAL		26

P6 Occupation

Respondidas: 26 Omitidas: 0

#	RESPUESTAS	DATE
1	Technician	3/8/2024 2:50 PM
2	Miljöstrateg	3/8/2024 11:12 AM
3	Eu and Strategic Funding	3/8/2024 9:44 AM
4	Project Manager	3/6/2024 1:25 PM
5	Environmental strategist	3/6/2024 11:07 AM
6	EU Project Coordinator	3/6/2024 9:03 AM
7	Technician	3/5/2024 1:40 PM
8	Technician	3/5/2024 1:32 PM
9	Environmental strategist at municipality	3/5/2024 10:11 AM
10	Technologist	3/5/2024 9:57 AM
11	Project Officer	3/5/2024 9:42 AM
12	project leader	3/5/2024 8:13 AM
13	Climate and environment strategist	3/5/2024 7:44 AM
14	Employed	3/4/2024 12:23 PM
15	Expert Advisor at a Regional Energy and Climate Agency	3/4/2024 11:26 AM
16	Researcher	3/1/2024 6:23 PM
17	engaged	3/1/2024 2:15 PM
18	Engineer	3/1/2024 2:14 PM
19	Public servant - Manager	3/1/2024 1:32 PM
20	Technical engineer	3/1/2024 8:37 AM
21	Manager og Agenda 2030 - Climate and energy	3/1/2024 8:31 AM
22	Techician at Energy Agency, Pamplona City Council	2/27/2024 12:56 PM
23	EU project manager	2/26/2024 9:51 AM
24	elevate qualification	2/23/2024 4:23 PM
25	Engineer	2/20/2024 9:14 AM
26	Officer	2/20/2024 9:09 AM

P7 Specify the scale of occupation (regional, local)

Respondidas: 24 Omitidas: 2

#	RESPUESTAS	DATE
1	Regional	3/8/2024 2:50 PM
2	Local (Municipality)	3/8/2024 11:12 AM
3	Local	3/8/2024 9:44 AM
4	regional	3/6/2024 1:25 PM
5	Local	3/6/2024 11:07 AM
6	Regional	3/6/2024 9:03 AM
7	Regional	3/5/2024 1:40 PM
8	Regional	3/5/2024 1:32 PM
9	Local	3/5/2024 10:11 AM
10	EU	3/5/2024 9:57 AM
11	European	3/5/2024 9:42 AM
12	regional	3/5/2024 8:13 AM
13	Local	3/5/2024 7:44 AM
14	local	3/4/2024 12:23 PM
15	Regional	3/4/2024 11:26 AM
16	National and European	3/1/2024 6:23 PM
17	local	3/1/2024 2:15 PM
18	Regional	3/1/2024 2:14 PM
19	local	3/1/2024 1:32 PM
20	local	3/1/2024 8:37 AM
21	Local	3/1/2024 8:31 AM
22	local	2/27/2024 12:56 PM
23	local	2/26/2024 9:51 AM
24	local	2/23/2024 4:23 PM

P8 Is there any legal framework to promote CET in your region/Nation?

Respondidas: 26 Omitidas: 0

OPCIONES DE RESPUESTA	RESPUESTAS	
No	15.38%	4
Yes, but only at regional level	7.69%	2
Yes, but only at national level	26.92%	7
Yes, both national and regional level	50.00%	13
TOTAL		26

P9 In case of existing framework(s) , could you name it (them)? Since when is in force?

Respondidas: 23 Omitidas: 3

#	RESPUESTAS	DATE
1	Ley Foral de Cambio Climático y Transición Energética Klina - Hoja de Ruta de Cambio CLimático PEN - Plan Energético de Navarra	3/8/2024 2:52 PM
2	Miljöbalken (1998) (alla verksamhetsutövare hushålla med energi och i första hand använda förnybara energikällor) Lagen kommunal energiplanering (1977) - Säger dock bara att konsekvenserna av en kommuns energiplanering på miljön, hälsan och hushållningen med mark och vatten och andra resurser ska analyseras.	3/8/2024 12:47 PM
3	Jobs and Climate Pact - Emilia Romagna Region; National Integrated Energy and Climate Plan 2030	3/8/2024 9:50 AM
4	there is a 1977 law on municipal energy planning through which it is mandatory for every municipality to have a plan for energy consumption, distribution and supply of energy. The law contains letters about the impact on the environment and is often interpreted in its entirety as requiring the municipalities to produce an energy and climate strategy.	3/6/2024 11:32 AM
5	Plan Nacional Integrado de Energía y Clima (PNIEC) 2021-2030 Plan Energética de Navarra 2030 Hoja de Ruta de Cambio Climático - KLINA Ley Foral de Cambio Climático y Transición Energética (del 22-03-2022)	3/6/2024 9:06 AM
6	National and regional Law in Climate Change and Energy Transition enacted. Is being developed "Estrategia de Transición a una Energía Limpia de Navarra 2030 y 2050" for example.	3/5/2024 1:46 PM
7	LFCCTE	3/5/2024 1:44 PM
8	Piano per la Transizione Ecologica (PTE) [Ecological Transition Plan (national level)]; Piano Nazionale Integrato per l'Energia e il Clima (PNIEC) [National Integrated Energy and Climate Plan]; Strategia Regionale per lo Sviluppo Sostenibile [Regional Strategy for Sustainable Development]; Legge Regionale 17 Febbraio 2023, n. 17 "FVGreen" [Regional Law 17 02/17/2023 "FVGreen" -> Decarbonization by 2045]; Piano Energetico Regionale (PER) [Regional Energy Plan].	3/5/2024 11:24 AM
9	Mainly "klimatklivet"	3/5/2024 10:12 AM
10	Since 1977 there is a national law for local energy plans	3/5/2024 7:46 AM
11	I have a general Knowledge about the topic, but I don't know the specific legal framework, as it is not part of my daily work.	3/4/2024 12:23 PM
12	National energy efficiency and renewables laws which have been in force for a long time	3/4/2024 11:34 AM
13	Climate Action Plan	3/1/2024 6:23 PM
14	PNIEC at national level (since 2021) PEN2030 (since 2018) and Regional Law on CC and CET (since 2022) at regional level	3/1/2024 2:20 PM
15	I don't know	3/1/2024 2:17 PM
16	Green Politics	3/1/2024 1:33 PM
17	- Plan de Acción para la Transición Energética 2018-2019 (Pamplona) - Ley Foral de Cambio Climático y Transición Energética 2022 (Navarra) - Ley 7/2021, de 20 de mayo, de cambio climático y transición energética (Spain)	3/1/2024 8:41 AM
18	no	3/1/2024 8:38 AM
19	Energy Transition and Climate Change Strategy 2030 (Pamplona City Council) Navarre Energy Plan Horizon 2030 (Regional) National Integrated Energy and Climate Plan (PNIEC) 2021-2030	2/27/2024 1:04 PM
20	Emilia Romagna: Regional law n. 5/2022 del 27 maggio 2022 National: Decreto Milleproroghe 162/2019 and following laws	2/26/2024 9:53 AM

21	D.L. 199/2021	2/23/2024 5:13 PM
22	Regional Law on Climate Change and Energy Transition	2/20/2024 9:16 AM
23	Navarre: Plan Energético de navarra Horizonte 2030 Hoja de ruta de cambio climático Ley Foral de Cambio Climático y transición energética España: Plan Nacional Integrado de Energía y Clima horizonte 2030	2/20/2024 9:16 AM

P10 Regarding your regional CET strategy, is it aligned with national, European and international strategies?

Respondidas: 26 Omitidas: 0

OPCIONES DE RESPUESTA	RESPUESTAS	
No	11.54%	3
Yes	88.46%	23
TOTAL		26

P11 Are the public policy objectives of energy systems clearly defined? Are they aligned with the energy transition?

Respondidas: 26 Omitidas: 0

OPCIONES DE RESPUESTA	RESPUESTAS	
They are not clearly defined	15.38%	4
They are clearly defined, but are not aligned with the energy transition	19.23%	5
They are both clearly defined and aligned	65.38%	17
TOTAL		26

P12 On a scale of 1 to 4, where 1 is the lowest value and 4 the highest, how important are the following possible needs for the governance system (GS) to achieve its objectives?

Respondidas: 26 Omitidas: 0

	1	2	3	4	TOTAL	PROMEDIO PONDERADO
Commitment of the stakeholders	0.00% 0	7.69% 2	26.92% 7	65.38% 17	26	3.58
Definition of common objectives	0.00% 0	11.54% 3	23.08% 6	65.38% 17	26	3.54
Policies involving the stakeholders	0.00% 0	7.69% 2	42.31% 11	50.00% 13	26	3.42
Promote effective participation and consensus building	0.00% 0	11.54% 3	42.31% 11	46.15% 12	26	3.35

#	OTHER (SPECIFY)	DATE
1	Coherence of measures and policies with the strategies and objectives	3/5/2024 11:57 AM
2	Awareness of the citizenship	3/1/2024 2:37 PM
3	Participation of the citizenship-4	2/20/2024 9:33 AM

P13 On a scale of 1 to 4, where 1 is the lowest value and 4 the highest, how important are the following requirements for the governance system to achieve its objectives?

Respondidas: 26 Omitidas: 0

	1	2	3	4	TOTAL	PROMEDIO PONDERADO
Strategy: The definition of objectives and the implementation of activities, programmes or the operating system of the governance system. The short and medium-term plans that enable it to adapt its mission to the context in which it operates and the organisational structure it adopts.	0.00% 0	3.85% 1	46.15% 12	50.00% 13	26	3.46
Control: Supervision of activities and professional staff and actions implemented at all times within the framework of applicable laws and regulations.	0.00% 0	3.85% 1	50.00% 13	46.15% 12	26	3.42
Sustainability: Governance must ensure the proper use of funds and have the acceptance (and eventual support) of society for the development of its activities	0.00% 0	3.85% 1	34.62% 9	61.54% 16	26	3.58

#	OTHER (SPECIFY)	DATE
1	Use of QUALITY TOOLS-KPI-....4	2/20/2024 9:33 AM

P14 On a scale of 1 to 4, where 1 is the lowest value and 4 the highest, rate the impact of the following barriers on the governance system

Respondidas: 26 Omitidas: 0

	1	2	3	4	TOTAL	PROMEDIO PONDERADO
Failure to gain broad stakeholder support and to prevent falling into an endless consultation process. Not being able to implement actions.	3.85% 1	11.54% 3	30.77% 8	53.85% 14	26	3.35
Lack of commitment and involvement by the agents involved.	3.85% 1	3.85% 1	38.46% 10	53.85% 14	26	3.42
Lack of resources (financial, staff, etc.)	3.85% 1	11.54% 3	46.15% 12	38.46% 10	26	3.19
Lack of transparency	3.85% 1	26.92% 7	38.46% 10	30.77% 8	26	2.96
'Numbness or introspection', in which the GS is more concerned about himself than about advancing the organisation and its mission or adapting to changes in the environment.	3.85% 1	19.23% 5	46.15% 12	30.77% 8	26	3.04

#	OTHER (SPECIFY)	DATE
1	Lack of coordination between departments and different public administrations (local, regional,...)-4	2/20/2024 9:33 AM

P15 How would you define the governance of your region?

Respondidas: 23 Omitidas: 3

#	RESPUESTAS	DATE
1	CET and Climate competences belong to different Government Departments and it's essential to cooperate. Navarra is a small region and main agents involved in CET are already identified	3/8/2024 3:01 PM
2	Skåne Region is ambitious in its energy strategy but face big challenges	3/8/2024 12:48 PM
3	A common path: the new Covenant establishes shared commitments and responsibilities to improve the quality of life for people and the planet and overcome the conflict between development and the environment.	3/8/2024 10:01 AM
4	Quite efficient	3/6/2024 9:14 AM
5	It is starting	3/5/2024 1:54 PM
6	Could be improved and needs more intersectoral interest	3/5/2024 1:53 PM
7	Weak, there is room for to listen to and involve more the stakeholders and citizens and to monitor the implementation of the strategies and plans, respecting milestones and their time scheduling	3/5/2024 11:57 AM
8	fairly decoupled from municipalities	3/5/2024 10:26 AM
9	right-wing	3/5/2024 9:15 AM
10	Well working but with limited power	3/5/2024 7:57 AM
11	Our Region is one of the most active in our country	3/4/2024 12:33 PM
12	Top-down and centralized. Most of the decisions are being made at the national level and passed down through the levels of governance without proper alignment	3/4/2024 11:41 AM
13	Strong	3/1/2024 6:27 PM
14	I believe that the local government has a clear objective of promoting local energy generation, rehabilitation of the housing stock, and passive construction standards, but with the mobility sector it is not acting in the same way. The percentage of energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions are too high in the mobility sector; There is much room for improvement in railway infrastructure, both for commuter and freight transport. I believe that changing from combustion vehicles to EV or hydrogen vehicles is not the solution. This strategy puts a disproportionate responsibility on citizens for the change in the model and what we really need is a change in the mobility model itself.	3/1/2024 2:56 PM
15	Very vertical and divided into different departments and administrations	3/1/2024 2:37 PM
16	Good governance	3/1/2024 2:26 PM
17	Good	3/1/2024 1:38 PM
18	Quite interest in ambient problems	3/1/2024 9:11 AM
19	lack of consensus and organisation to implement certain actions, such as one-stop-shops integrating various services at regional level (energy rehabilitation, urban regeneration, inclusion of RES, energy poverty, renaturalisation, etc.).	2/27/2024 1:29 PM
20	Regional centric	2/26/2024 9:58 AM
21	busy but slow in processes	2/23/2024 5:29 PM
22	The government of Navarra is made up of hierarchically ordered bodies. Each Department has a Technical General Secretariat and is structured into one or several General Directorates.	2/20/2024 9:33 AM
23	Vertical system	2/20/2024 9:33 AM

P16 What should it look like in the future/what do you imagine it will look like?

Respondidas: 22 Omitidas: 4

#	RESPUESTAS	DATE
1	Real cooperation horizontal (between Navarra's Government Departments) and vertical (including Local Action Groups, Public Enterprises and Local Entities).	3/8/2024 3:01 PM
2	Broader interaction between governmental agencies working towards the same goal, more implemented actions rather than investigations/reports	3/8/2024 12:48 PM
3	Enhanced spaces for the whole territory and for new generations	3/8/2024 10:01 AM
4	Maybe a bit more, still, of citizen participation	3/6/2024 9:14 AM
5	With a stable and organized governance system	3/5/2024 1:54 PM
6	Much more transversal than now	3/5/2024 1:53 PM
7	I hope it will have a more bottom up approach with a strong coordination which is able to collect and properly harmonize all inputs received	3/5/2024 11:57 AM
8	stronger governance with more mandatory requirements on the municipalities	3/5/2024 10:26 AM
9	More funding to public transport, bikelanes and hospitals etc	3/5/2024 9:15 AM
10	More power to the regional planning (from the national level)	3/5/2024 7:57 AM
11	It is necessary to invest money and efforts in improving the energy efficiency of our building	3/4/2024 12:33 PM
12	We need aggregation of the regional level into fewer larger and more powerful regions with dedicated resources and more bottom-up decision making	3/4/2024 11:41 AM
13	collaborative	3/1/2024 6:27 PM
14	As I have said before, a change of mobility model should be developed, shared and multimodal. On the other hand, citizen-driven energy communities should be promoted from the bottom up, by citizens, without being dictated by energy companies.	3/1/2024 2:56 PM
15	Common collaboration among administrations (national, regional, local). Involve citizenship in the process of elaborating policies.	3/1/2024 2:37 PM
16	In the future I hope more attention	3/1/2024 2:26 PM
17	More Green	3/1/2024 1:38 PM
18	I don't have a clear imagine of the future because a lot of people is non responsible about environment and not interest in clean energy	3/1/2024 9:11 AM
19	The services offered to the different actors involved are centralised, shared, and organised at regional level without duplication.	2/27/2024 1:29 PM
20	facilitation envelop clean energy on territory	2/23/2024 5:29 PM
21	In my opinion this is a good structure	2/20/2024 9:33 AM
22	Working in project between different departments in multidisciplinary teams	2/20/2024 9:33 AM

P17 What should be the level of involvement of each stakeholder to achieve the following objectives? (select from drop-down menu).

Respondidas: 26 Omitidas: 0

Establishing rules and principles to help manage and control organizations and instit...

Protecting the rights of shareholders and stakeholders in organizations.

Distribution of roles and responsibilities through tight organizational structures.

Coordinate alignment with national, international and European level strategies and e...

Encourage the participation of citizens and social and economic actors in the develop...

Establishing rules and principles to help manage and control organizations and institutions					
	1	2	3	4	TOTAL
Citizens	26.92% 7	38.46% 10	15.38% 4	19.23% 5	26
Companies	23.08% 6	19.23% 5	50.00% 13	7.69% 2	26
Public administrations	7.69% 2	3.85% 1	23.08% 6	65.38% 17	26
Professional associations	7.69% 2	30.77% 8	46.15% 12	15.38% 4	26
Social environmental associations	3.85% 1	23.08% 6	57.69% 15	15.38% 4	26
Building an environment of trust, transparency and accountability.					
	1	2	3	4	TOTAL
Citizens	11.54% 3	46.15% 12	23.08% 6	19.23% 5	26
Companies	7.69% 2	15.38% 4	50.00% 13	26.92% 7	26
Public administrations	7.69% 2	7.69% 2	11.54% 3	73.08% 19	26
Professional associations	0.00% 0	23.08% 6	50.00% 13	26.92% 7	26
Social environmental associations	0.00% 0	34.62% 9	38.46% 10	26.92% 7	26

Protecting the rights of shareholders and stakeholders in organizations.					
	1	2	3	4	TOTAL
Citizens	15.38% 4	38.46% 10	26.92% 7	19.23% 5	26
Companies	11.54% 3	11.54% 3	57.69% 15	19.23% 5	26
Public administrations	3.85% 1	7.69% 2	34.62% 9	53.85% 14	26
Professional associations	3.85% 1	19.23% 5	65.38% 17	11.54% 3	26
Social environmental associations	7.69% 2	23.08% 6	38.46% 10	30.77% 8	26
Distribution of roles and responsibilities through tight organizational structures.					
	1	2	3	4	TOTAL
Citizens	30.77% 8	46.15% 12	3.85% 1	19.23% 5	26
Companies	15.38% 4	19.23% 5	38.46% 10	26.92% 7	26
Public administrations	7.69% 2	0.00% 0	19.23% 5	73.08% 19	26
Professional associations	0.00% 0	23.08% 6	46.15% 12	30.77% 8	26
Social environmental associations	7.69% 2	15.38% 4	50.00% 13	26.92% 7	26
Coordinate alignment with national, international and European level strategies and encourage participation in EU or international networks and initiatives					
	1	2	3	4	TOTAL
Citizens	30.77% 8	34.62% 9	23.08% 6	11.54% 3	26
Companies	15.38% 4	30.77% 8	30.77% 8	23.08% 6	26
Public administrations	8.00% 2	0.00% 0	16.00% 4	76.00% 19	25
Professional associations	0.00% 0	26.92% 7	50.00% 13	23.08% 6	26
Social environmental associations	3.85% 1	30.77% 8	26.92% 7	38.46% 10	26
Encourage the participation of citizens and social and economic actors in the development and implementation of planning instruments regarding CET					
	1	2	3	4	TOTAL
Citizens	15.38% 4	30.77% 8	19.23% 5	34.62% 9	26
Companies	3.85% 1	19.23% 5	50.00% 13	26.92% 7	26
Public administrations	8.00% 2	4.00% 1	8.00% 2	80.00% 20	25
Professional associations	0.00% 0	23.08% 6	42.31% 11	34.62% 9	26
Social environmental associations	7.69% 2	0.00% 0	30.77% 8	61.54% 16	26

#	OTHER (SPECIFY)	DATE
1	Politicians-4-4-4-4-4	2/20/2024 9:33 AM
2	Third sector associations	3/5/2024 11:57 AM

P18 According to the following development stages of a governance system, in which stage is your region currently? - First stage: GS members are relatively homogeneous in terms of personal thinking and commitment to the organisation. It is usually a fairly small council and tends to have a more informal structure.- Second stage: It emerges when the organisation has achieved greater maturity and the GS's attention shifts. It focuses more on classic governance questions such as planning, oversight and accountability. Committees are formed and the number of directors increases. The consequence is a more defined structure.- Third stage: GS members are strategically recruited, there are committees to develop the work, an executive committee to prepare complex decisions, and in some cases an advisory committee with external experts.

Respondidas: 24 Omitidas: 2

OPCIONES DE RESPUESTA	RESPUESTAS	
First stage	25.00%	6
Second stage	62.50%	15
Third stage	12.50%	3
TOTAL		24

P19 What management tools can help governance systems develop structures that improve governance strategies? For instance:- Collection of regional energy data from multiple sources to prepare the Navarre Energy Balance (annual) to monitor regional KPIs (PEN2030).- Use of statistical tools and technology platforms to monitor energy management at local and regional level (EIS in Navarra).- The creation of a monitoring tool for SECAPs (agreements reached, planning and actions executed and monitoring of results).

Respondidas: 19 Omitidas: 7

#	RESPUESTAS	DATE
1	Outline the strategic framework and guidelines for subsequent operational agreements and implementation strategies needed to achieve the shared goals.	3/8/2024 10:01 AM
2	The creation of a monitoring tool for SECAPs	3/7/2024 3:30 PM
3	The three example are correcto: energy data available and transparent, statistical tools, and online monitoring systems. Everything public, updated and transparent.	3/6/2024 9:14 AM
4	a new tool for governance. All of the above examples only with information repositories	3/5/2024 1:54 PM
5	Currently there is PEN2030, EIS platform or a SECAPs monitoring tool. Hence, I do not have any idea.	3/5/2024 1:53 PM
6	- Platform where all the actors (both public and private) publish their objectives, plans and milestones/deadlines and show the progress constantly in order to increase transparency and commitment through public accountability; - a monitoring tool to collect all data about SECAPs monitoring reports and track actions and progress in the implementation (since the Region promote the drafting of SECAPs by Municipalities).	3/5/2024 11:57 AM
7	Provide energy balances to municipalities to make sure decision on all levels are based on the same baseline of the energy system.	3/5/2024 10:26 AM
8	Strategic planning and risk management tools	3/5/2024 9:52 AM
9	Do not know	3/5/2024 7:57 AM
10	Use of statistical tools and technology platforms to monitor energy management at local and regional level	3/4/2024 12:33 PM
11	Tools to support integrated planning and data management	3/4/2024 11:41 AM
12	All of the above	3/1/2024 6:27 PM
13	Monitoring tool on best practicies on CET actions at local and regional level.	3/1/2024 2:37 PM
14	The creation of a monitoring tool for SECAPs	3/1/2024 2:26 PM
15	Collection of regional energy data from multiple sources to prepare the Navarre Energy Balance (annual) to monitor regional KPIs (PEN2030).	3/1/2024 1:38 PM
16	The creation of a monitoring tool for SECAPs (agreements reached, planning and actions executed and monitoring of results)	3/1/2024 9:11 AM
17	statistics tools and tecnologia platform to monitor energy management at local and regional level	2/23/2024 5:29 PM
18	Some system to know the problems/concerns of citizens and adapt strategies to them	2/20/2024 9:33 AM
19	Quality tools to aid the continuous improvement	2/20/2024 9:33 AM

P20 Define which review and evaluation mechanisms the governance system should have in order to detect early on possible deviations from the achievement of the objectives. (Multiple choice)

Respondidas: 26 Omitidas: 0

OPCIONES DE RESPUESTA	RESPUESTAS
Fostering a culture of monitoring, evaluation and learning among public officials by increasing their capacity to regularly conduct exercises for these purposes in collaboration with relevant stakeholders.	88.46% 23
Identifying institutional actors to be in charge of collecting and disseminating up-to-date and reliable information and data in an open format.	46.15% 12
Periodic review of regional and local KPIs to monitor targets and identify any early deviations. In the event of deviations, identification of their causes. Finally, application of corrective measures.	80.77% 21
Critical points balance sheets	19.23% 5
Instruments for measuring efficiency: relationship between the resources used in the implementation of actions and the products and effects of the action.	53.85% 14
Other (please specify)	3.85% 1
Total de encuestados: 26	

#	OTHER (PLEASE SPECIFY)	DATE
1	These mechanism are all important and interesting. The problem is that local authorities don't have enough personells and time.	3/4/2024 12:33 PM

PLAN4CET

PARTNERS

Gobierno de Navarra
Nafarroako Gobernua

Ayuntamiento de Pamplona | Iruñeko Udala

Nasuvinsa
Navarra de Suelo y Vivienda, S.A.

eurac
research

FEDARENE

zabala
INNOVATION

ENERGIKONTOR
SYD

Comune di Parma

PROVINCIA
DI PARMA

AESS

ATES PARMA
AGENZIA TERRITORIALE ENERGIA SOSTENIBILITÀ